

Antwerp Management School

Master Thesis

Critical success factors of adoption to a (SaaS) public cloud.

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Abstract

With digital transformation becoming more important, companies are switching more often to Software as a Service (SaaS) solutions. However the advent of cloud computing is having an increasing impact on enterprise IT architecture and how the components of the governance process is executed. Many companies tend to simply assume that moving IT systems to the cloud will directly yield benefits provided by the cloud infrastructure and systems. However, this approach can often result in more complex and costly IT architectures. While the value of switching to a cloud strategy has to be maximized. What is needed, is to identify the impact and key success factors of the adoption of SaaS and how to use these to successfully adopt to SaaS.

In order to identify this, this thesis master document will provide an overview of a general set of critical success factors for cloud adoption from an overall, governance and architecture point of view. This is based on a literature review as a research methodology. Critical success factors were identified in already existing literature, these were then verified with several industry experts. To cover all aspects of the validation by industry experts with regards to cloud SaaS and get observations from different angles, three target groups have been selected; Cloud customer, cloud supplier and cloud broker.

Research has been done from an architecture perspective, to determine whether the reviewed enterprise architecture frameworks such as Zachman (1987), The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF) (Harrison 2011), Dynamic Architecture (DYA) (Jumelet, 2009) and the adaptive enterprise architecture framework (Gill, 2015) can be used to develop adaptive enterprise architecture for cloud adoption. Moreover how these can support the critical success factors. From a governance perspective research and comparison of most popular governance frameworks and standards such as COBIT, COSO, ITIL, ISO 27000, ISAE 3402 and CCM have been done.

In different countries all over the world research has been done into identifying the critical success factors of cloud adoptions in the past. Articles about these studies have been collected and several critical success factors were identified. Namely information Security, data Security, cost, relative advantage, complexity, compatibility, trialability, top management support, technological readiness, firm size, IT managers support, service level agreements and monitoring, regulatory environment, service providers support, perceived industry pressure.

Based on the overall results of the interviews with the industry experts it can be concluded that in general they are in agreement on what is important and what is not. From an architecture and governance point of view for the broker, provider as well as the customer, data security and information security are of high importance. However these two factors also have one of the highest difference in valuation amongst these groups. Therefore, these factors need extra attention in order to ensure expectations are aligned. In general it can be concluded from the overall findings that almost all critical success factors found in literature have importance except perceived industry pressure.

Keywords related to master thesis.

These are the keywords: Cloud, SaaS, Adoption, Critical Success Factors, IT governance models, Cloud governance, Architecture models, Cloud architecture, Enterprise architecture.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In this section the objective of the master thesis research is explained. Furthermore the problem statement is addressed, namely a low success rate in cloud adoption. Lastly the main research question, “What are the critical success factors of adoption to a public cloud (SaaS) from an IT governance and Enterprise architecture point of view?” is discussed in this section.

1.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

More and more organizations are very dependent on IT for the creation of their business value (Steven De Haes, 2018). In order to enable digital transformation many organizations are adopting to the rapidly growing technology called cloud computing. According to a recent Gartner report (2018) Software as a Service (SaaS) remains the largest segment of the cloud market, with revenue expected to grow 17.8 percent to reach \$85.1 billion in 2019. In addition “The increasing adoption of SaaS applications and other cloud services impacts the management, dissemination and exploitation of enterprise content,” states Craig Roth, research vice president at Gartner (Gartner, 2018).

So, in a world where digital transformation is becoming more important, we see that the trend of public cloud solutions has gained popularity and many large organizations have successfully implemented specific SaaS solutions. Nonetheless many of them are struggling to get the full value out of their investment (McKinsey, 2018).

The value of cloud investments is low, because the advent of cloud computing is having an increasing impact on enterprise IT architecture and how the components of the governance process is executed. Many companies tend to simply assume that moving IT systems to the cloud will directly yield benefits provided by the cloud infrastructure and systems. However, this approach can often result in a more complex and costly IT architectures. In order to maximize the value of switching to a cloud strategy, it is needed, to identify the impact and key success factors of the adoption of SaaS and how to use these to successfully adopt to Public cloud (SaaS) (McKinsey, 2018).

The problem is a low success rate for cloud adoption.

1.2 MAIN RESEARCH QUESTION

Related to the problem statement the following main research question will be addressed:

What are the critical success factors of adoption to public cloud computing (SaaS) from an IT governance and enterprise architecture point of view?

To support this, the following sub research questions have been defined.

- What are identified critical success factors for cloud adoption?
- How can architectural models support cloud adoption?
- How do IT cloud governance models support cloud adoption?

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2 RESEARCH METHOD

A lot of research has been done on the topic of cloud adoption for various sectors, industries and use cases. However, there is no overview of a general set of critical success factors (CSF's) for cloud adoption. In fact many of these articles contradict each other on what the CSF's are. Therefore, the goal of this research is to provide an overview of the CSF's and exploring the collective evidence in this area. In order to achieve this, literature review as a research methodology has been chosen. (Snyder, 2019)

The literature review has been divided in three phases, as described below:

- Phase 1 Design & Conduct
- Phase 2 Analysis
- Phase 3 Review & Conclusion

2.1 DESIGN & CONDUCT

As mentioned before, cloud adoption is a contemporary theme and the interest in this topic is growing continuously. However, many companies are struggling with adopting to cloud. Even cloud brokers and providers are struggling and researching how they can support their customers during the process of adopting to cloud. Therefore, for this review the strategy will consist of 2 parts. Firstly, following a specific research strategy, a great deal of the literature available in the academic world will be evaluated. Secondly, the results will be validated by experts from the practical world, with a general overview of the CSF's of cloud adoption as result.

For the validation by experts, we will use qualitative methods, as they are designed to help the researchers understand the theoretical phenomena. While quantitative analysis aims to isolate specific aspects of phenomena by measuring them by means of dedicated tools, its specific focus means that it lacks in consideration of the wider setting in which the phenomena occur. Qualitative analysis however enables researchers to study social and cultural phenomena. The study of why people make decisions and act the way they do is often highly contextual. To explore this very context, qualitative research methods are developed to provide theories about why the phenomenon happened in the way they occur. Qualitative methods are analytical enquiry techniques that examine phenomena in a real-life context. They are especially helpful when you want to study a specific phenomenon in depth. These are well adapted for exploratory research where a phenomenon is still not fully understood, is not well studied or is still evolving. These are also suitable for researching a phenomenon's social cultural or political aspects. Compared to quantitative research, qualitative methods include various philosophical assumptions, data collection techniques, and techniques for analysis and interpretation (Recker, 2013).

Qualitative approaches are designed to help researchers create an overall, detailed picture of complex phenomena. This typically involves shedding light on a phenomenon from multiple perspectives, creating a broader picture and paying attention to different facets of the phenomenon without isolating or limiting it to one or a few dedicated variables. Quantitative methods are based

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on random sampling, where cases are randomly selected from a wider population. In contrast, qualitative methods rely on purposeful sampling, where cases are chosen because they possess certain interesting properties. Qualitative methods have distinct advantages because they can potentially reveal complex multifaceted, or even concealed phenomena and can lead to a more detailed, multi-perspective view (Recker, 2013).

Qualitative methods employ a variety of techniques to gather data. The most prominent form is conducting an interview, either face-to-face, one-to-many (in focus groups) or by telephone/conferencing (Recker, 2013). While questionnaires can provide evidence of patterns amongst large populations, qualitative interview data often gathers more in-depth insights on the thoughts of participants and their attitudes and actions. (Kendall, 2008).

Usually interviewing uses relatively explicitly organized procedures, depending on the intent of the interview. The interviews are in general of a semi-structured type. In these, a predefined interview structure (a protocol) asks respondents about the topics of the study. The interview is progressing flexible as new questions can be brought up as a result of what the interviewee says during the interview. Thereby, the interview follows a conversational form allowing for follow-up questions and bidirectional discussion of the topic (or other topics and links that emerge during the interview). Semi-structured interviews usually begin with more general questions, or with topics. Usually these questions are formulated before interview. Yet the possible relationships between the questions, theoretically related topics and issues become the basis for more concrete (normally not pre-formulated) questions. This approach allows for flexibility for both the interviewer and the person being interviewed to search for information or discuss issues if necessary or advantageous. Semi-structured interviewing is thus guided only in the sense that some form of interview protocol provides a framework for the interview. To that end, semi-structured interviews exhibit a number of benefits over other interviewing approaches (Recker, 2013):

- For those being interviewed, they are less intrusive as semi-structured interviews facilitate two-way communication. For example, those being interviewed may ask questions to the interviewer.
- It can be used to validate what's already understood while at the same time offering learning opportunities. The details derived from semi-structured interviews will often not only provide responses but also explanations into the reasoning behind these responses.
- When people are interviewed individually and in a conversational rather than formal way, they may address sensitive issues with greater ease.

2.1.1 Approach

For the search of literature for the literature review, the following criteria were used:

- Keywords or a combination of keywords to initiate search
 - Cloud, SaaS, Adoption, Critical Success Factors, IT governance models, Cloud governance, Architecture models, Cloud architecture, Enterprise architecture.
- Trustworthy sources

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- The search for articles/information will be limited to official websites which are known for collecting and/or publishing academic research.
- Research from the last 10 years
 - Cloud is a relative new topic, therefore most research will be from the last few years. However, to ensure that the review is based on recent research and findings a limit has been set of ten years. Only in exceptional cases, for instance if the data is found to be still relevant and up to date, will older research be used.
- Research articles/papers relevant for this review.
 - All research found and used must be relevant to the review and support in addressing the problem statement.

To cover all aspects of the validation by industry experts with regards to SaaS and get observations from different angles, the goal is to interview 3 target groups. These groups are also the main audience of this research. As illustrated in Figure 1 in the conceptual model this research is focused on the CSF's of adoption to SaaS as seen by IT governance and Enterprise IT architecture. Interviewing these target groups will give a great advantage in creating a clear picture by giving insights from various angles into the process and workings of cloud adoption.

Figure 1 Conceptual model research

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For selecting the right number of interviewees, purposeful sampling will be used. The logic and power of purposeful sampling lie in selecting information-rich cases for study in depth. Information-rich cases are those from which one can learn a great deal about issues of central importance to the purpose of the inquiry, thus the term purposeful sampling. Studying information-rich cases yields insights and in-depth understanding rather than empirical generalizations. (Patton, 2002)

The following selection criteria will be used:

1. Cloud customer
 - Companies who are currently using cloud solutions or are in transition to a cloud solution.
 - At least two different companies and two employees in direct relation to this topic will be interviewed.
 - The interviewee has an architectural or governance role.
 - The interviewee is currently involved in cloud adoption and/or has been involved in cloud adoption.
2. Cloud provider
 - Companies who are currently providing cloud solutions to customers.
 - At least one company and one employee with direct relation to this topic will be interviewed.
 - The interviewee has an architectural or governance role.
 - The interviewee is involved in the process of providing cloud solutions to customers including the adoption process.
3. Cloud Intermediary / broker
 - Companies which supply cloud solutions to customers but do not have their own cloud.
 - At least two different companies and two employees with direct relation to this topic will be interviewed.
 - The interviewee is involved in the process of providing cloud solutions to customers including the adoption process.

For this research ten different people were interviewed in total.

2.2 ANALYSIS

CSF is a common concept, used for example in the context of project management, quality management and software engineering. In the literature there are various definitions for a critical success factor:

“CSF’s are, for any business, the limited number of areas in which results, if they are satisfactory, will ensure successful competitive performance for the organization. They are the few key areas where “things must go right” for the business to flourish. If results in these areas are not adequate, the organization’s efforts for the period will be less than desired. As a result, the CSF’s are areas of activity that should receive constant and careful

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attention from management. The current status of performance in each area should be continually measured, and that information should be made available. (Rockart, 1979).”

“The limited number of areas in which results, if they are satisfactory, will ensure successful competitive performance for the organization’. They are the few key areas where ‘things must go right’ for the business to flourish. As a result, the CSFs are areas of activity that should receive constant and careful attention from management. The current status of performance in each area should be continually measured, and that information should be made widely available (Ward & Peppard, 2002).”

“A limited number of factors the business success or failure depends on. Critical Success Factors are the things that have to fall into place in order to reach the business objectives (Lecklin, 2006).”

While the CSF is established, it is important to notice that ‘critical’ factors should be differentiated from ‘important’ factors (Ward & Peppard, 2002). Generally, CSF’s are time sensitive and time dependent, so they should be reviewed as much as needed to keep up with the current business climate (McNurlin & Sprague, 2002)

Based on the various definitions of CSF’s as described above, the following conclusions can be made. They have to be done exceptionally well in order to have the solution that is migrated from an on-premises environment to a public cloud (SaaS) environment, fully adopted by the internal organization which in turn ensures that the business reaches its objectives and gains more value. During the selection of this research’s CSF’s from the literature, above stated has been taken into account.

2.3 REVIEW & CONCLUSION

When the literature has been collected and the interviews conducted, the found CSF’s from the literature are being validated and the results will be reviewed. The review will be split up in 3 different sections, overall, governance and architecture. This in order to comply with the research questions and the focus of the two domains (governance & architecture).

The conclusion will be based on the findings and linked to the research questions. In addition to make impact and recommendation will be part of the conclusion.

For this research following research boundaries have been identified:

- The research focus is on companies located in the Netherlands because the outcome of the research can vary if the research is focussed on different countries.
- The research doesn’t focus on companies in a specific domain because the outcome of the research can vary if the research is focussed on companies in a specific domain.
- The research focus is on companies of an enterprise size (this means more than 500 employees) because the outcome of the research can vary if the research is focussed on smaller sized companies.

3 RESEARCH

Swiftly and surely, the world is shifting to SaaS. It's becoming the fact delivery model for core business applications. By 2022, the growth in enterprise IT expenses for cloud-based offerings will be faster than the growth in traditional (non-cloud) IT-offerings. Making cloud computing one of the most disruptive forces in IT markets since the early days of the digital age. (Gartner, 2019).

Cloud technologies propose numerous advantages over on-premises technologies. Companies are eager to adopt evolving cloud technologies which suits the context of their company. The adoption of a cloud is not just migrating applications, services and workload to the cloud. Companies need an adaptive cloud enterprise architecture capability to support iterative cloud-enabled enterprise adaptation (Gill, 2015).

Since this is a duo thesis, research has been done from the perspective of architecture and governance on success factors of cloud adoption. To start with some background information of cloud, will be explained in chapter 3.1, following with research of cloud Enterprise Architecture described in chapter 3.22 then the research of cloud Governance will be described in chapter 3.3. Ending the research with CSF's we have identified in the literature.

3.1 BACKGROUND CLOUD

In recent years the trend of cloud solutions has gained popularity and introduces many benefits, causing many companies to switch their strategy from in housing to cloud solutions. The advent of cloud computing has an increasing impact on enterprise IT architecture and how the components of the governance process are executed (Maches, 2010). Mass movement to digital business and cloud computing is changing the way businesses and government adapt to digital disruptive forces. Emerging trends now show 40% of the IT budget being spent by the business (Gill, 2015).

A commonly acknowledged definition of cloud computing is provided by the US National Institute of Standard and Technology (NIST).

"Cloud computing is a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction. (Mell & Grance, 2011)"

According to that definition, this model stimulates availability and is composed of five essential characteristics, four deployment models and three service models

The five essential characteristics according to Mell & Grance (2011) are:

- **On-demand self-service:** Consumer can individually provision automatic computing capabilities without requiring human interaction with the cloud provider.

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- **Broad network access:** Services are available all over the network and accessed through standard mechanisms for example mobile phones, tablets, laptops, and workstations. The service is available on any place and anytime.
- **Resource pooling:** The provider’s computing resources are pooled to serve multiple customers using a multi-tenant model, with different physical and virtual resources dynamically assigned and reassigned according to consumer demand.
- **Rapid elasticity:** Computing Resources can be elastically up scaled and down scaled, in some cases automatically.
- **Measured service:** Cloud systems automatically control and optimize resources usage. These resources can be controlled, monitored, and reported, providing transparency for the consumer.

According to Mell & Grance (2010), the deployment models are defined as follows:

Private Cloud: The cloud infrastructure is provisioned for exclusive use by a single organization comprising multiple consumers (e.g., business units). It may be owned, managed, and operated by the organization, a third party, or some combination of them, and it may exist on or off premises.

Public Cloud: The cloud infrastructure is provisioned for open use by the general public. It may be owned, managed, and operated by a business, academic, or government organization, or some combination of them. It exists on the premises of the cloud provider.

Hybrid Cloud: The cloud infrastructure is a composition of two or more distinct cloud infrastructures (private, community, or public) that remain unique entities, but are bound together by standardized or proprietary technology that enables data and application portability (e.g., cloud bursting for load balancing between clouds).

The three service models according to Mell & Grance (2011) are:

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS): The capability provided to the consumer is to provision processing, storage, networks, where the customer is able to deploy and run arbitrary software, including operating systems and applications. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, and deployed applications, and possibly limited control of select networking components (e.g., host firewalls).

Platform as a Service (PaaS): A platform-based service allowing customers to develop, run, and manage applications without the complexity of building and maintaining the infrastructure typically associated with developing and launching an app. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, or storage, but has control over the deployed applications and possibly configuration settings for the application-hosting environment.

Software as a Service (SaaS): An application delivery model that enables users to utilize a software solution over the Internet. SaaS revenue models are typically subscription based, where users pay a fixed recurring fee over a period of time (often monthly or annually). The customer does not manage

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or control the underlying cloud infrastructure including network, servers, operating systems, storage, or even individual application capabilities, with the possible exception of limited user-specific application configuration settings.

Gartner also defines SaaS as software that is owned, delivered and managed remotely by one or more providers. The provider delivers software based on one set of common code and data definitions that is consumed in a one-to-many model by all contracted customers at any time on a pay-for-use basis or as a subscription based on use metrics (Gartner, 2019).

3.1.1 Hype Cycle

The Gartner Hype Cycle provides a graphic representation of the maturity and adoption of technologies and applications, and how they are potentially relevant to solving real business problems and exploiting new opportunities. The Gartner’s Hype Cycle methodology gives a view of how a technology or application will evolve over time (Gartner, 2019). While SaaS was still in the stage of the Slope of Enlightenment in 2012, by 2018 it had already reached the plateau of productivity. Meaning that the technology mainstream adoption starts to take off. The technology’s broad market applicability and relevance are clearly paying off.

Figure 2 Gartner Hype Cycle SaaS

3.1.2 Stakeholders

Cloud computing not only involves technology adoption, but also involves a number of stakeholders or actors who interact with each other, play different roles and engage in relevant activities in the cloud environment. An actor could be a human or non-human individual or organization (Gill, 2015).

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Role	Activities
Customer	Cloud customer pays for the cloud service and use it.
User	Cloud user or consumer uses the cloud service.
Developer	Cloud developer develops the cloud service.
Provider	Cloud provider provides the cloud service.
Manufacturer	Cloud manufacturer manufactures the cloud service.
Tester	Cloud tester tests the cloud service.
Integrator	Cloud integrator integrates the cloud service.
Manager	Cloud manager manages the cloud service.
Owner	Cloud owner owns the cloud service.
Administrator	Cloud administrator administrates the cloud service.
Carrier	Cloud carrier provides the connectivity and network to connect the cloud service.
Broker	Cloud broker manages the interactions between cloud actors.
Auditor	Cloud auditor conducts an independent audit of the cloud service.
Regulator	Cloud regulator provides the standards and regulatory compliance requirements for the cloud service.
Observer	Cloud observer observes or monitors the cloud service.
Partner	Cloud partner supports the cloud provider.
Competitor	Cloud competitor is in competition with another cloud actor.

Table 1 Overview Stakeholders

3.1.3 Cloud adoption benefits

Adoption of public cloud computing is increasing in interest among both public and private organizations. Cloud computing claims to offer several benefits over traditional computing. Some of these benefits are described in the upcoming sub chapters.

Enhanced Enterprise Agility

Public cloud claims to enhance enterprise or business agility. SaaS provides flexibility to an enterprise to quickly scale up and down (vertical scaling) and scale in and out (horizontal scaling) in response to dynamic business needs. Vertical scaling is the capability to enhance the capacity of existing hardware or software by adding resources. Horizontal scaling is the ability to connect multiple hardware or software entities, such as servers, so they work as a single logical unit in response to changing business demands. SaaS applications enable enterprises to choose the delivery model and easily change it when business requirements change. It is simpler to integrate into other systems and to enable additional set of components on demand. (Beaumont, 2014) (Gill, 2015).

Reduced Costs

There are two categories: capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX). Every enterprise has its own thoughts on how to establish cloud Return of Investment (ROI). For many enterprises it is CAPEX versus OPEX. Cloud computing shifts IT investments to a pay-as-you-go model.

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Enterprises only pay for what they use, when they use it. Cloud computing seems to reduce the upfront capital cost of new IT resources and the cost of ongoing ownership. Cost is not only incurred due to IT equipment or software, it also includes human resources (Cloud Technology Partners, 2019) (Gill, 2015).

Reduced Carbon Emission

Companies could reduce their carbon emissions by 50 percent if they migrate their IT resources to the cloud. Several cloud computing providers have replaced fuel with green energy to power up their datacentre. Numerous cloud hosting providers now introduce hydro, wind, or solar energy as a component in their energy requirements. Therefore, migrating workloads to cloud resources or developing new ones in a cloud-native environment can be an organization's way of going green and achieving sustainability. Also, consumers do not have to keep their computing resources up and running all the time. They can source cloud computing resources from the cloud provider on a need basis, and switch them off when they are not required any more (The Guardian, 2011) (Advani, 2019).

Improved Resource Utilisation

Cloud computing revolves around the proper utilization of datacentre resources. Fundamental to cloud computing is the virtualisation of physical resources. Virtualization is the process of creating a software-based, or virtual, representation of something, such as virtual applications, servers, storage and networks with a view to improving physical resource utilisation (VMware, 2019).

Improved Reliability

Cloud computing covers various types of resources. These resources allow enterprises to quickly detect, adapt and recover from a failure or disaster situation. SaaS solutions are hosted by a SaaS provider, so all upgrades, installations, maintenance, and new users are connected to the system without any effort on the customer's side (MacDonald, 2019) (Gill, 2015).

Improved Availability

Cloud computing allows cloud consumers to pay only for the required availability times. It increases the ability of a cloud consumer to minimize unwanted downtime or interruptions due to planned or unplanned changes. All upgrades of SaaS applications are automatically installed without downtime or interruptions (MacDonald, 2019) (Gill, 2015).

3.1.4 Cloud adoption challenges

Even though public cloud offers many profitable advantages over on-premises computing, it brings new challenges as well. These challenges will be discussed in the upcoming sub chapters.

Security

According to a study by Logic Monitor, 66% of IT professionals say security is their greatest concern in adopting an enterprise cloud computing strategy (Columbus, 2018). Security refers to the ability of the cloud to handle security threats such as malware and denial-of-service. SaaS providers will deliver the same version of the software to all kind of companies over the globe. Meaning a significant investment into security, which would be expensive to achieve independently for a locally installed application. SaaS will be run across multiple datacentres providing full redundancy in case

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one goes down and will have continuous data backups. SaaS will include the latest security protocols, SLAs for uptime and complete separation of data to satisfy data privacy policies (MacDonald, 2019).

Compliance

Cloud providers may have their resources accommodated at different datacentres around the globe. It is important for a cloud provider to address local and international legal compliance requirements. While not a regulation per se, ISO/IEC 27001 is a standard that a cloud provider can choose to comply with, to manage information security risks. Optionally, it can also be used as a guideline for formal compliance assessment in order for your organization to become certified by accredited certification auditors (Ullian, 2019).

Privacy

Research shows that privacy is one of the top concerns preventing firms from moving to SaaS (Wang Y.-H. , 2011). A public cloud is a multitenant environment which is used by multiple enterprises. It is important to ensure that cloud providers have appropriate access control measures to counter any privacy breaches or unauthorised access to the information stored in the multitenant shared environment (Gill, 2015).

Portability

There are many SaaS providers. When an enterprise locks into one SaaS provider, the enterprise also accepts that specific SaaS provider's standards, protocols and tools, which can complicate a cloud migration. Proprietary standards also limit the portability of applications, if you decide to move from one vendor to another, there is a need to develop standards for cloud (Pahl, Zhang, & Fowley, 2014).

Interoperability

Interoperability is the ability to share information between different cloud and non-cloud environments. There is limited interoperability of information between clouds. Similar to the portability challenge, there is a need to develop standards for cloud (Pahl, Zhang, & Fowley, 2014).

Social

Cloud adoption is not only about the technological aspects. Successful cloud adoption requires that social challenges needs to be identified and addressed. These challenges may include organisational culture, human behaviour, and the political environment of an enterprise. In successful adoption of cloud computing people's motivations and mindsets are critical elements.

3.2 CLOUD ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE

Companies that wish to migrate their IT services to a cloud face several challenges. The uncertainties about the challenges and issues involved in this technology are reasons for not accepting cloud technology as a reliable solution by many organizations (Conway and Curry, 2010). Indeed, the migration to a Public cloud does not present a clear path: adopting Public cloud without proper assessment and analysis may in itself become a major risk. The lack of criteria to support IT managers' decision-making can cause uncertainties and create obstacles in the adoption of this technology (Duarte and Silva, 2013). Prompted by this gap in knowledge about Public cloud, an extensive review of the literature has been done in order to compile issues that point to important, enterprise architecture aspects. These aspects should be taken into account by organizations when considering migrating their technological structure to public cloud.

Enterprise architecture is a blueprint that can be used to describe the overall structural, behavioural, social, technological, and facility elements of a cloud technology-enabled operating environment that share common goals and principles (Gill, 2015). It defines the integration and standardization requirements for business processes and IT infrastructure (Ross et al. 2006). Enterprise architecture aligns IT to business, enabling business to achieve its goals.

There are a variety of well-known enterprise architecture frameworks such as Zachman (1987), The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF) (Harrison 2011), Dynamic Architecture (DYA) (Jumelet, 2009) and the adaptive enterprise architecture framework (Gill, 2015). These frameworks have been reviewed to establish whether they can be used for developing adaptive enterprise architecture for cloud adoption. The question is which enterprise architecture framework is most appropriate for developing and implementing the adaptive enterprise architecture to realize the SaaS strategy with the highest success rate of adopting to this new cloud technology. The success rate of successful adopting Public cloud depends on the organizations ability to have a clear vision and the ability to transform the organization towards that vision. (Gill, 2015)

The development and management of complex adaptive cloud enterprise architecture isn't always easy. Applying enterprise architecture is criticized for not delivering or showing the value early because enterprise architecture approaches may take a few months to years to develop cloud technology-enabled fixed enterprise architecture for realizing cloud adoption strategy. Organizations need an adaptive agile enterprise architecture capability for iteratively developing and managing the cloud technology-enabled adaptive enterprise architecture. An enterprise architecture is said to be an agile or adaptive enterprise architecture when it adapts to expected or unexpected changes at any time, reacts appropriately to expected and unexpected changes, focuses on reducing waste and cost without compromising on quality, accommodates expected or unexpected changes rapidly and focuses on improvement, transformation and innovation (Gill, 2015).

In the context of adaptive cloud enterprise architecture capability establishment for cloud adoption, the before mentioned frameworks will be reviewed in the following sections.

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3.2.1 Zachman Framework

The Zachman Framework is an ontology-based enterprise architecture framework used for organizing enterprise architecture processes and artefacts. The Zachman Framework does not provide an enterprise architecture process for implementing and running an enterprise architecture capability. However, it provides a way of viewing an enterprise and its information systems from different perspectives. The Zachman Framework is a structured two-dimensional matrix defining six enterprise architecture views (Figure 3): contextual, conceptual, logical, physical, detailed and functioning (Zachman 2008). The row headers of this matrix represent the enterprise architecture views. The column headers of this matrix define the motivation (why), function (how), data (what), people (who), network (where) and time (when) elements.

The Zachman Framework also does not provide a concrete enterprise architecture implementation methodology. However, it provides a generic and structured ontology that can be used in tailoring a situation-specific adaptive cloud enterprise architecture capability.

Figure 3 Zachman Framework

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3.2.2 Dynamic Architecture

DYA (short for Dynamic Architecture) is an approach to enterprise architecture from Sogeti – Netherlands. DYA is primarily focused on the process of architecting in general, more specifically on the development and improvement of the architecture function. To summarize DYA has the following principles (DYA, 2019):

- Architecture is not the end goal itself but should support the goals an enterprise wants to achieve.
- Architecture should be developed piece by piece, so it can evolve in line with the organization.
- Changes to the architecture can sometimes be necessary.

The DYA model is the core of Dynamic Architecture (Figure 4) and consist of four processes covering all phases between strategy and realization. DYA is complimented by an architecture framework, although with less detail and emphasis.

Figure 4 DYA Framework

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DYA recognizes the creation of enterprise and domain (business unit level) architectures. They form the fundament for the creation of project start architectures, which provide projects with architectural objectives and constraints. A project start architecture contains a context model, scoping of the proposed IT solution, design criteria and standard guidelines.

The benefit of the DYA approach is its attitude towards Enterprise Architecture, which is absolutely pragmatic: “just enough, just in time”. It provides at the right time for the right purpose, the right stakeholders with the right Enterprise Architecture documentation. The DYA strategy focuses on specific business strategies rather than abstract goals which emphasize flexibility and agility. DYA describes how to embed architecture within an organization and offers descriptions of processes, architectures, architecture team and governance of architecture. Needless to say, the DYA approach does not imply any long-term strategic planning beyond individual business initiatives potentially undermining the general strategic effectiveness. For that reason, the DYA approach is best applied within organizations operating in very vibrant, dynamic and unpredictable environments and markets (Kotuse, 2016).

3.2.3 The Open Group Architecture Framework

The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF) (Harrison 2011) is a comprehensive generic framework for developing and maintaining enterprise architecture capability. It is a standard approach for assisting in the acceptance, production, use, and maintenance of Enterprise Architectures. It is based on an iterative process model supported by best practices and a re-usable set of existing architectural assets. TOGAF provides the architecture development method (ADM), templates, guidelines, techniques, content meta-model (CM), enterprise continuum, and a technical reference model (TRM). A partial view of the TOGAF (A-H phases of the ADM) is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 The Open Group Architecture Framework

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The ADM is a major component of the TOGAF framework. ADM has nine phases: Preliminary, Architecture Vision, Business Architecture, Information System Architecture, Technology Architecture, Opportunities and Solutions, Migration Planning, Implementation Governance, and Architecture Change Management. These phases can be iteratively executed for establishing an enterprise architecture capability; developing the vision, business, information systems, technology and solution architectures; performing implementation and migration planning and governance; and managing changes in the enterprise architecture capability and design (TheOpenGroup, 2019) (Wagner, 2014).

The nine ADM phases applied to building a cloud architecture are explained in the following sectors:

PHASE A: ARCHITECTURE PHASE

In phase A, a description of the high-level architecture which reflects the cloud-based nature of the architecture that is envisioned will be fabricated. There are some apprehensions which are specific to SaaS in terms of privacy, data security compliance, ROI, transparency and scalability. During this phase these apprehensions need to be identified.

PHASE B: BUSINESS ARCHITECTURE

The overall business goals will not change while migrating to a SaaS solution, the Business users themselves will be variable in a SaaS scenario and hence this view may need to be adjusted for different groups that the SaaS service will accommodate.

The business architecture has to manage privacy, security and other quality attributes of SaaS applications. Governance, controllability and visibility are other important factors of serious consideration.

PHASE C: INFORMATION SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

In this phase, variations are required, similarly to phase B. A cloud application's core entity relationship modelling may match that of its traditional on-premise application equivalent. However, some critical changes need to be made to cloud-ready applications.

Applications to be transformed into SaaS must abstract some conventional components that are part of the Application Architecture View and thus vary from a traditional business application.

The data security view process models would vary from those of an on-premise program. Data integration can be a challenge for cloud computing as it drives information back into siloes that may not be directly accessible by the IT department. It is also worth evaluating the classifications of information and privacy and prioritizing the risk requirements for both cloud-based and on-site data.

PHASE D: TECHNOLOGY ARCHITECTURE

Because of cloud applications, this view will be the one that will experience the greatest changes compared to a normal application. TOGAF will be used for the process of assessing the current capability and to scope the future to be environment.

Within the application architecture, SaaS can abstract some common elements that are part of the Application Architecture View, making this view different from a traditional enterprise application.

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PHASES E&F: OPPORTUNITIES AND SOLUTIONS/ MIGRATION PLANNING

During these phases, it is of the utmost importance that the cloud's available capabilities are fully understood. Only then the services that are candidates for a cloud transformation can be identified.

Instead of providing a standardized ROI (return on investment) or a cost benefit analysis to justify the products that need to be purchased or charged-back for assets that need to be agreed on in advance, the business can provide operational expenditure outlines. Overall, what matters is a clear definition of the value that cloud will bring to the business.

PHASE G: IMPLEMENTATION GOVERNANCE

For this phase it is worth to consider including the following activities on top of the standard:

- Security and operations implementation. (Security as a Service)
- Business processes (Process as a Service)
- Applications (Application as a Service)
- Technical services (Storage as a Service and Infrastructure as a Service)
- Data (Information as a Service and Database as a Service)

It is easier to govern architecture usage within the enterprise when the design and development team are familiar with, and conform to, the cloud API and services. Although the enterprise architecture team hasn't traditionally been relevant to the operational side of the organisation, this does seem to be changing with the cloud. After all the common cloud management platform provides the relevant tools for management and reporting, and takes away the burden of patch management, version upgrades, high availability, disaster recovery, and so on.

PHASE H: ARCHITECTURE CHANGE MANAGEMENT

Phase H's objective is to set up an architecture change management process for the new baseline of enterprise architecture that is accomplished during the completion of phase G. Conventionally, this mechanism provides close monitoring of topics such as new technological innovations, developments in the business environment, and for deciding whether a new phase of architectural evolution should be initiated.

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3.2.4 Adaptive Cloud Enterprise Framework

The adaptive enterprise architecture framework is a meta-framework that can be used to support the tailoring of a situation-specific adaptive enterprise architecture capability or framework (Gill, 2015). This framework provides a support for developing and managing adaptive or agile enterprise architecture in a modern context including adaptive cloud technology enabled enterprise architecture.

This framework has two main layers (see Figure 6): an outer layer and an inner layer. The outer layer represents the five adapting capabilities (e.g. assessment, rationalisation, realisation, un-realisation and context awareness) to guide the continuous adaptation of the adaptive enterprise architecture as an adaptive enterprise service system in response to internal and external changes. The inner layer assists in defining, operating, managing, and supporting the complex enterprise as an adaptive enterprise service system in response to changes or requirements reported by the outer layer.

Figure 6 Adaptive Cloud Enterprise Framework

Outer Layer

The five enterprise architecture adaptation capabilities that are presented in the outer layer (Figure 6) can be used to guide the continuous adaptation of the cloud environment: context, rationalisation, assessment, realisation and unrealisation (Gill, 2015).

Context awareness

Context awareness concerns the ongoing monitoring and scanning of cloud service adoption prospects for business-level improvements or adjustments. In the outer layer, the scope enables iteratively to identify and examine the contextual information related to the cloud-enabled operating environment enterprises.

Rationalisation

Rationalisation covers the continuous scanning and sensing opportunities for changes and improvement or at the individual ability or service level (vertical). It includes analysing and identifying services that can be supported or replaced through cloud technology.

Assessment

Assessment interprets and analyses cloud adoption or change opportunities identified both at the context and rationalisation stages and uses the adaptive enterprise architecture as a lens. In order to detect the current opportunities and enterprise readiness for adopting the specific cloud services, assessment focuses on the evaluation of intelligence offered in the context model. At this stage, based on their cloud readiness evaluation results, one may choose to proceed with the adoption or de-adoption of cloud services.

Realisation

Realisation includes the making of decisions and performing of actions needed to actually implement the cloud service. It also assists with the overall management of complex adoption and improvement of a cloud environment, (both from technological and economic point of view). This provides a cloud adoption roadmap, integrated engagement, governance and cloud project portfolio support. It also includes actions related to consolidation of local and legacy IT systems and their integration with the cloud environment.

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Unrealisation

Unrealisation refers to a situation where a cloud adoption opportunity is delayed and not (yet) realized. This includes identifying opportunities for cloud adoption that are not applicable at the time but could be reconsidered in the future. It is also important to document why a cloud adoption opportunity is not realised or relevant.

Figure 7 Outer Layer, Adaptive Cloud Enterprise Framework

Inner Layer

The inner layer of the framework (see Figure 6) is connected to the outer layer and presents an architecture as a living system of service systems (e.g. holistic view of the enterprise, agencies, business units), which is called the adaptive enterprise service system architecture. The adaptive enterprise service system architecture has four elements: defining, operating, managing and supporting (Gill, 2015).

Defining

To establish the cloud adaptive enterprise architecture capability, the identification, selection and implementation of the best architecture practices, roles, tools and cloud reference architecture are required. It also includes understanding the boundaries and scope of the cloud architecture before assigning any cloud architecture development and implementation work.

Operating

To realise the enterprise cloud strategy, the ability to actually operate the architecture capability for developing and implementing the cloud-enabled adaptive enterprise architecture. This includes defining factory and facility architectures and the cloud-enabled interaction architecture. Factory architecture includes developing human focused business, information and social architectures; and

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cloud focused applications (SaaS). Interaction architecture defines the complex dynamic interactions between internally and externally sourced cloud service systems.

The cloud service factory approach to cloud is important as it draws attention to the re-usability and service supply chain which includes sourcing of services to support the cloud adoption strategy of the enterprise. To develop the cloud service system solution architecture, it is operated as a cloud service system factory that integrates the in-house built and externally sourced services in the public cloud.

Managing

This capacity combines key management disciplines such as enterprise requirements strategy, project and service management, architecture for managing the whole cloud adoption environment. To iteratively define the requirements for cloud services, enterprise cloud requirements management is required.

Enterprise cloud strategy is required to provide which and at what time capabilities and services will be deployed in the cloud. To develop and manage the cloud-enabled current, transition and future architecture, enterprise cloud architecture management capability is required. This is linked to enterprise service and project management capabilities.

To iteratively implement the cloud-enabled adaptive enterprise architecture, enterprise cloud programs, projects, portfolio and iterations are required and included in enterprise project management.

Enterprise cloud service management is necessary to provide ongoing operational support once the cloud services are utilized in the production environment.

Supporting

Outer and inner layers of the adaptive enterprise architecture framework provide an agile and integrated holistic service systems approach to deal with the complex cloud adoption strategy. The Supporting capability is required to enhance core management disciplines through intelligence, asset library and method engineering.

3.2.5 Review of the well-known frameworks

The review of these well-known frameworks suggests that The Zachman framework only provides the architecture taxonomy and does not provide any concrete enterprise architecture guidelines and/or methods. DYA describes how to embed architecture within an organization and offers descriptions of processes. However, DYA does not describe how to architect nor does it describe which steps related to content have to be taken to produce a good architecture. The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF) provides the most comprehensive architecture method and guidelines to develop the enterprise cloud architecture. However, the challenge with TOGAF is

twofold: firstly, it is heavy, slow and documentation driven. Secondly, it needs to be customized to the organisation needs. It is unlikely that it can be used or adopted off-the-shelf for any specific organisation. Organisations need to tailor their enterprise architecture framework that suits their specific needs where the adaptive cloud enterprise framework besides TOGAF could come in place.

3.3 CLOUD GOVERNANCE

Why is IT governance important?

In the current day and age a lot of companies are moving towards the cloud. By doing this a lot of processes and a lot of corporate knowledge and information moves to the cloud. This brings a lot of risks and therefore requiring better security Not only in regards to the architecture, but also the usage and control. IT governance can support here by establishing best practice set of rules and controls. However a traditional governance framework could no longer be effectively be solved in the cloud. Therefore, existing frameworks are transforming, and new ones are appearing in order to support governance in the cloud. As this is needed in order provide visibility and IT control so operational risks can be reduced and compliance established.

Overview of IT governance models

In order to have any discussions about IT governance models and how they can contribute to cloud adoption, it is important to have an understanding of the standards and frameworks that apply to IT governance. Research and comparison of most popular governance frameworks and standards have been done. For example by Reijnders (2017) who looked at the different cloud governance models and identified the following: COBIT, COSO, ITIL, ISO 27000, ISAE 3402 and CCM. He also looked at how they can support with cloud computing and This will be used as a basis to perceive how these can contribute to the CSF's of cloud adoption.

3.3.1 COBIT

COBIT was first released in 1996 and represents control objectives for information and related technology. With its current version being COBIT 2019. As indicated by ISACA (2012) Its strategy is: "to look into, create, distribute and advance a definitive, forward-thinking, global arrangement of by and large acknowledged data innovation control targets for everyday use by business directors, IT experts and confirmation experts." Initially, COBIT was a review structure for auditing however in the long run developed in a ground-breaking IT governance control model.

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Figure 8 COBIT 2019 Core model

One of the new concepts that was also introduced in COBIT is the focus area concept. This describe a certain governance topic which can be addressed by a collection of governance and management objectives and their components. This also includes the focus area concept of cloud computing.

3.3.2 COSO

The 'Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission' ('COSO') is a joint initiative to combat corporate fraud. They are dedicated to providing thought leadership via the development of frameworks and guidance on enterprise risk management, internal control and fraud deterrence (COSO, 2020).

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Figure 9 COSO Framework

Coso, I. I. (2004). Enterprise Risk Management. Integrated Framework.

It is a model which is mainly used for evaluating and designing of risk management. It identifies the relation between company risks and internal control systems.

3.3.3 ITIL

ITIL stands for Information Technology Infrastructure Library. ITIL is a widely adopted body of knowledge and best practices for successful IT service management that links with training and certification. ITIL 4 has transformed from version 3 by re-shaping much of the established ITSM practices in the wider context of customer experience, value streams and digital transformation, as well as embracing new ways of working, such as Lean, Agile, and DevOps. The latest form of the ITIL framework, ITIL® 4, was released in February 2019. It's a huge update from ITIL V3 which was used for more than 10 years.

The aim of ITIL4 is to provide guidance to organizations when it comes to facing new challenges on the perspective of service management and developing/potential modern technology. It is designed to ensure a flexible, coordinated and integrated system for the effective governance and management of IT-enabled services.

3.3.4 ISO 27000

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is a worldwide federation of national standards bodies. The series is in general broad in scope and covers things such as privacy, confidentiality, IT & cybersecurity. For example the ISO 27000 series also offers standards for cloud risk assessment tools. The ISO 27001, for example, is the best practice for information security management systems. It can be applied to all kinds of organizations from small to large, and it encourages organizations to assess their information risks and mitigates these accordingly. Given the changing nature of information risk and security, the concepts incorporate continuous feedback and improvement activities to respond to changes in the threats, vulnerabilities or impacts of incidents. (ISO, 2020)

3.3.5 ISAE 3402

ISAE 3402 is a globally recognized standard for assurance reporting on service organizations. (Fanning, 2014). The difference between this standard and ISO27001 is that ISAE 3402 has a framework that gives additional assurance. If operational processes are within cloud this can have direct impact on the Financial Statement. Meaning this is also relevant from an accounting point of view. Accountants do not understand the value of a ISO 270001 standard, however the ISEA 3402 standard is recognized by them as this can be used for the control of the financial statements. One of the drawbacks is a lack of detail in regard to information security, thus other frameworks are used for this. However the added value of ISAE is that next to the security parts of ISO 27001 also all processes including the cloud process that have effect on the financial statement are included.

3.3.6 CCM

The cloud control matrix (CCM) was created by the cloud security alliance (CSA). It provides a standard when it comes to securing the cloud environment. The CCM is a framework with cloud specific security controls, which are mapped to best practices and regulations. It is developed with industry players, cloud service providers, governments and enterprises.

It covers three main focus areas: cloud architecture, governing in the cloud and operating in the cloud. In addition there are over a 100 controls and guidelines to use the matrix. This will help to support and understand the relevance of security requirements for the cloud consumer, provider and vendor and their roles and responsibility in implementing each control. (Sankar, 2015)

3.3.7 Overview of cloud governance models

Already many different IT control governance frameworks exist. Research by Reijnders (2017), links different governance frameworks to the cloud governance dial by Becker and Bailey (2014), which indicates that the different governance models all cover something for cloud computing and on which cloud domain the governance framework is applicable as can be seen in Table 2 & Table 3.

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Frameworks	Risk Domain	Governance by	Cloud Domains
ITIL	Event Risk	Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strategic Decision Making ▪ Operational Processes ▪ Finances
ISO 27000 series	Security Risk	Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Security and Compliance
COBIT	Business Risk	Standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strategic Decision Making ▪ Environmental ▪ Market Positioning ▪ Finances ▪ Operational Processes ▪ Security and Compliance
COSO	General Risk	Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strategic Decision Making ▪ Environmental ▪ Market Positioning ▪ Finances ▪ Operational Processes ▪ Security and Compliance
CCM	Business Risk	Standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Operational Processes ▪ Security and Compliance
ISAE 3402	Engagement Risk	Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Operational Processes ▪ Security and Compliance

Table 2 Cloud Governance Frameworks (Reijnders, 2017)

Frameworks	Definition Cloud Computing	Definition Risk	Definition Governance	What does the framework offer for Cloud computing
ITIL	A framework for allowing easy on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g. storage, network, compute, applications and services) that can be easily distributed and released with minimal effort or interference of the service providers.	An event that may cause harm or loss, or affect the ability to achieve goals. A risk is measured by the probability of a threat, the asset's exposure to that threat, and its effects if it happened.	Governance is used to empower people, is agile, allows process automation, and defines the measurement and control mechanisms that enable people to tactilely do their daily jobs in order to achieve strategic goals of the "IT governance" programs.	ITIL provides best practice guidance to service providers on the provision of quality IT infrastructure and the processes, functions and other capabilities needed to support them. ITIL can be capitalized on and provide a solid foundation for the management of cloud-based services and hybrid IT environments.
ISO 27000 series		The potential for a given threat to exploit an asset or asset group's vulnerabilities and thus cause harm to the organization. It is measured in terms of a combination of the likelihood of an event occurring and its impact.	Ensure that information security is consistent with business strategies and priorities, quality implementation and transparency. Supports the achievement of compliance, agility, visibility, effectiveness and efficiency.	For both cloud service customers and cloud service providers, provide more detailed guidance and recommendations.
COBIT		The business risk of using, owning, running, affecting, controlling, implementing and adoption of IT within an organization.	The board and executive management set out responsibilities and procedures with the goal of providing strategic direction, ensuring targets are achieved and ensuring that risks are properly managed.	Produce a summary assessment of the business risks and achieve an application's business value, and help practitioners assess many security or value issues (often to a highly granular degree).
COSO		A computing resource deployment and procurement model that allows an organization to obtain its computing resources and applications through an Internet connection from any location.	Risk is the potential for an occurrence to occur and adversely affect the achievement of goals.	A process, carried out by the board of directors, management, and other staff of an entity, applied throughout the enterprise and in the setting of strategies, designed to identify potential events that may affect the entity, and to manage risk within its risk appetite, to provide

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			<i>reasonable assurance as to the achievement of entity objectives.</i>	
CCM	<i>A design to allow flexible on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, databases, space, software, and services) that can be easily distributed and released with minimal management effort or interference between service providers.</i>	<i>The business threat of using, owning, running, affecting, controlling and implementing IT in a company or organization</i>	<i>Ensure the cloud protection requirements are met through the standards that are given.</i>	<i>Provide basic principles of security to guide cloud vendors and assist prospective cloud customers in assessing a cloud provider's overall security risk.</i>
ISAE 3402		<i>Engagement risk: the risk of financial loss and harm to his or her professional reputation from the auditor's disclosure.</i>	<i>Ensure that processes, process management and safety are in line with the enterprise standards.</i>	<i>Provide managers, customer organizations and other stakeholders (clients, for example) of a service organization with information on the controls that the service organization has in place.</i>

Table 3 Cloud Governance Frameworks (Reijnders, 2017)

3.3.8 Framework benefits to Cloud Computing

The frameworks all have their own benefits. As indicated by the search done by Reijnders (2017) every governance framework has its own benefits with regards to cloud computing, as can be seen in the overview at Table 4 below.

Governance Framework / Standard	Benefits to Cloud Computing
COBIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on a positive ROI of IT-enabled business investments • Manage IT-related business risk • Establish service continuity and availability • Create agility in responding to changing business requirements • Achieve cost optimization of service delivery • Lower process costs • Manage business change • Manage product and business innovation
COSO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud policies and controls • Assessments of the CSP control environment • Data classification policies and processes • Management oversight and operations monitoring controls • Incident management • Monitoring of the external environment • Preparation of an exit strategy • New disclosures in financial reporting
ITIL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Relationship Management—form and uphold the cloud service provider and customer business relationship. • Demand Management—understand, anticipate and influence business demand for services. • Carefully calculate demand to allocate the agreed budget within the financial management process. • Financial Management for IT Services—provide a cost-effective administration of the assets and resources used in providing IT services. Incorporate charging based on consumption when perusing cost analysis calculation. • Service Portfolio Management—describe a service provider's services in terms of the business value and needs. Create a portfolio for all potential external cloud deployment models. • IT Service Management—Asses the service provider's offerings, capabilities, competitors as well as current and potential market spaces to develop a strategy to serve customer needs.
ISO 27000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish the risk management context • Quantitatively or qualitatively assess (i.e. identify, analyse and evaluate) relevant information risks, taking into account the information assets, threats, existing controls and vulnerabilities to determine the likelihood of incidents or incident scenarios, and the predicted business consequences if they were to occur, to determine a 'level of risk'; • Treat, avoid and/or share the risks appropriately, using those 'levels of risk' to prioritize them; • Keep stakeholders informed throughout the process; and • Monitor and review risks, risk treatments, obligations and criteria on an ongoing basis, identifying and responding appropriately to significant changes
ISAE 3402	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security – The system is protected against unauthorized access (both physical and logical). • Availability – The system is available for operational use as committed or agreed. • Processing integrity – System processing is complete, accurate, timely and authorized. • Confidentiality –Information designated as confidential is protected as committed or agreed. • Privacy – Personal information is collected, used, retained, disclosed and destroyed in conformity

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> with the commitments in the service organization’s privacy notice, and with criteria set forth in generally accepted privacy principles issued by the AICPA.
CCM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emphasizing business information security control requirements Reducing and identifying consistent security threats and vulnerabilities in the cloud Providing a standardized security and operational risk management Seek to normalize security expectations, cloud taxonomy and terminology, and security measures implemented in the cloud.

Table 4 Framework benefits to cloud Computing (Reijnders, 2017)

3.4 SUCCESS FACTORS FOR SAAS ADOPTION.

In different countries all over the world research has been done into identifying the CSF’s of cloud adoptions in the past. An overview of these studies can be found in table 4. The studies from Azam et al (2013) research some CSF’s, which will cause a SME’s to adopt to cloud based services or not. They discovered that determining which cloud delivery model fits, is a decision driven by business needs and desired functionality. This depends on the size of the enterprise and the kinds of data, applications and processes in the enterprise (Azam, Razak, Marjan, & Mahyar, 2013). To conclude, they state that top management support plays a significant role, as does the firm size, and technical readiness. In the research of Tiago et al. (2014) technical readiness is also one of the CSF’s, which they state is a facilitator of cloud computing. According to their findings, an established infrastructure and workforce with the right skills and competence are better suited for cloud integration. However, it is interesting that different research from Low et al. (2011) suggests that technology readiness is irrelevant for the technology sector.

CSF’s from different researches have been collected and the TOE Framework was used to frame them. The TOE Framework is described in Tornatzky and Fleischer’s "The Processes of Technological Innovation" (1990). This framework is used a lot, especially for adoption. The TOE framework is an organization-level theory , which describes that three different elements of a firm’s context influence adoption decisions. These three elements are the technological context, the organizational context, and the environmental context. All three are positioned to influence technological innovation (Baker, 2011). Table 5 gives an overview of the CSF's which have been identified and their sources. A description of these CSF's will be given below.

NO	Critical success factor	Sources
T1	Information security	(Pfarr, Chowanetz, & Winkelmann, 2013)
T2	Data security	(Al-Mascati & Al-Badi, 2016) (Jiunn-Woei, David, & Yen-Ting, 2014) (Yeboah-Boateng & Essandoh, 2014) (Pfarr, Chowanetz, & Winkelmann, 2013)
T3	Cost	(Pfarr, Chowanetz, & Winkelmann, 2013) (Tiago, 2014) (Lorraine, 2013) (Pfarr, Chowanetz, & Winkelmann, 2013)
T4	Relative advantage	(Low, Chen, & Wu, 2011) (Jiunn-Woei, David, & Yen-Ting, 2014) (Tiago, 2014) (Lorraine, 2013) (Hans, Bouchaib, Hauke, & Fiona, 2013) (Margaret & Trisha, 2012) (Yazn, 2012) (Azam, Razak, Marjan, & Mahyar, 2013) (Wang, Wang, & Yang, 2010)

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T5	Complexity	(Low, Chen, & Wu, 2011) (Jiunn-Woei, David, & Yen-Ting, 2014) (Tiago, 2014) (Lorraine, 2013) (Mark & Dietmar, 2014) (Hans, Bouchaib, Hauke, & Fiona, 2013) (Margaret & Trisha, 2012) (Yazn, 2012) (Azam, Razak, Marjan, & Mahyar, 2013) (Wang, Wang, & Yang, 2010)
T6	Compatibility	(Low, Chen, & Wu, 2011) (Jiunn-Woei, David, & Yen-Ting, 2014) (Yeboah-Boateng & Essandoh, 2014) (Tiago, 2014) (Lorraine, 2013) (Mark & Dietmar, 2014) (Hans, Bouchaib, Hauke, & Fiona, 2013) (Margaret & Trisha, 2012) (Yazn, 2012) (Azam, Razak, Marjan, & Mahyar, 2013) (Wang, Wang, & Yang, 2010)
T7	Trialability	(Lorraine, 2013) (Mark & Dietmar, 2014) (Yeboah-Boateng & Essandoh, 2014) (Yazn, 2012)
O1	Top management support	(Low, Chen, & Wu, 2011) (Jiunn-Woei, David, & Yen-Ting, 2014) (Yeboah-Boateng & Essandoh, 2014) (Tiago, 2014) (Hans, Bouchaib, Hauke, & Fiona, 2013) (Yazn, 2012) (Ifinedo, 2011) (Azam, Razak, Marjan, & Mahyar, 2013) (Wang, Wang, & Yang, 2010)
O2	Technological readiness	(Low, Chen, & Wu, 2011) (Jiunn-Woei, David, & Yen-Ting, 2014) (Yeboah-Boateng & Essandoh, 2014) (Tiago, 2014) (Azam, Razak, Marjan, & Mahyar, 2013) (Wang, Wang, & Yang, 2010)
O3	Firm Size	(Low, Chen, & Wu, 2011) (Tiago, 2014) (Hans, Bouchaib, Hauke, & Fiona, 2013) (Yazn, 2012) (Azam, Razak, Marjan, & Mahyar, 2013) (Wang, Wang, & Yang, 2010)
O4	IT managers support	(Lorraine, 2013) (Yazn, 2012)
O5	Service level agreements and monitoring	(Pfarr, Chowanetz, & Winkelmann, 2013)
E1	Regulatory environment	(Jiunn-Woei, David, & Yen-Ting, 2014) (Tiago, 2014) (Mark & Dietmar, 2014) (Hans, Bouchaib, Hauke, & Fiona, 2013) (Yazn, 2012)
E2	Service providers support	(Jiunn-Woei, David, & Yen-Ting, 2014) (Yeboah-Boateng & Essandoh, 2014)
E3	Perceived industry pressure	(Low, Chen, & Wu, 2011) (Jiunn-Woei, David, & Yen-Ting, 2014) (Tiago, 2014) (Hans, Bouchaib, Hauke, & Fiona, 2013) (Yazn, 2012) (Ifinedo, 2011) (Azam, Razak, Marjan, & Mahyar, 2013) (Wang, Wang, & Yang, 2010)

Table 5 Critical success factors

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Figure 10 Number of sources Critical Success Factors

3.4.1 Critical success factors.

T1 Information security; According to Stéphane Hurtaud (2014), security concerns are still one of the major barriers to mass adoption of cloud. Security can be considered as one of the key considerations for SaaS acceptance. Therefore, providers must make sure that they have the highest possible level of security in place and communicate this to current and potential users of their SaaS application. In regards to security, two aspects need to be specifically accentuated.

First, the difference between actual and perceived security of information needs to be considered. With a SaaS solution organizations have to store their sensitive data outside of their traditional datacentre. Which means a perceived loss of control, and thus resulting in a security risk, even when the level of security measures that are maintained by the SaaS provider is the equivalent or better than the on premise solution. Providers must consider this barrier thoroughly and clearly communicate how they ensure information security in their solution (BSI, 2012).

Second, particular companies based in the EU are subject to strict laws, which forbid storing certain information on servers outside of the EU or even their own country. SaaS providers as well as (potential) users need to keep this aspect in mind during the service selection phase (BSI, 2012).

T2 Data security; One of the key elements that always comes up, when discussing cloud adoption, is data security. Placing your data in a cloud solution, can bring certain risks. As placing your data in a cloud solution can bring certain risks. Therefore this has been identified as a CSF. Al-Mascati & Al-Badi (2016) investigated whether data security concerns discourage the adoption of cloud computing

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technologies. However, this hypothesis was found to be unsupported. Their research found that cloud computing adopters were not concerned with data security. However, this contradicts other researches. For example Jiunn-Woei et al. (2014), found that data security was the most dominant when it comes to the technology dimension of their TOE framework, and considered it the most critical of the CSF's for cloud adoption.

T3 Cost; One of the drivers for an organization to move to a cloud solution is costs. The question however, is whether this is a CSF when it comes to the adoption of cloud solution. Jiunn-Woei et al. (2014) found that next to data security cost is the most dominant factor in the technology dimension. In addition, the study of Lorraine (2013) and Yeboah-Boateng & Essandoh (2014) confirmed that one of the key drivers revealed reduced cost and thus cost savings for IT purchases and maintenance for cloud adoption.

T4 Relative advantage; With this is meant the extent to which innovation is better than previous generation. What Tiago Oliveira et al. suggests is that relative advantage is found to have a positive influence on the adoption of cloud computing (Tiago, 2014). This finding is also consistent from findings from similar studies, for example Tan (2011), Wang et al. (2010) and Pfarr et al. (2013) had similar results. These 4 studies confirm that cloud adoption is positively influenced by the relative advantage it can bring. As it improves quality of operations, provide new business opportunities and increased productivity. However, on a comparative note the research of Low et al. (2011) indicated that it was negatively related to adoption of cloud computing and even seen as a barrier.

T5 Complexity; of business processes or operations can act as a barrier to the adoption of cloud computing technologies, as most cloud technologies are developed to meet the needs of multiple businesses, so that the more complex or unique operations a company preserves the less chance of adopting cloud computing technologies (Tiago, 2014). The literature research of Low et al. (2011) showed that the complexity can act as a barrier to the adoption of cloud computing. Also, the research of Jiunn-Woei et al. (2014) confirmed that complexity is in the top 5 of most critical factors. However what is interesting is that the research performed by Low et al. (2011) concluded in the end that complexity was not found to be significant for cloud adoption.

T6 Compatibility; refers to the degree to which innovation fits with the potential adopter's existing values, previous practices and current needs (Rogers, 1983). Here the findings of Low et al. (2011) indicated that compatibility is not significant for cloud adoption. This is however contradicting with other studies for example from Wang et al. (2010) as they found that it had a significant positive effect on the decisions of adopting to cloud.

T7 Trialability; is the degree to which an innovation may be experimented with on a limited basis (Rogers, 1983). Some studies have found this as an important component in the adoption as it may for example lead to familiarity of cloud solutions which can increase the acceptance. (Yazn, 2012)

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O1 Top Management Support; when the management of the organization understand the relevance of cloud computing, they tend to play a crucial role in influencing the organisation to accept it. This hypothesis was investigated by Ifinedo (2011) and his research confirmed that this is an important factor. Contradictory by the research of Wang et al. (2010), concluded the opposite and actually concluded that top management support is a non-significant discriminator.

O2 Technological Readiness; or also called technology competence consists of information technology, infrastructure and IT professional. Including the infrastructure platform, knowledge and skills to implement cloud computing. Also here the research of Wang et al. (2010) concluded that this factor is non-significant for cloud computing. This was also confirmed by a research of Low et al. (2011) which in both cases was inconsistent with previous studies they researched.

O3 Firm Size; is an interesting CRSF as it is questioning to what extend the cloud adoption is affected by the size of the company adopting to cloud. Low et al. (2011) researched the hypothesis whether Firm size will be positively correlated with the adoption of cloud computing. And they found that in their research Firm Size is one of the 5 drivers for cloud adoption, and with that also being a significant discriminator between cloud computing adopters and non-adopters.

O4 IT managers Support; is specific for IT management instead of top management which is organisation wide. The reason why this is a separate CRSF is because IT management might feel threaten by their position while moving to the cloud. Not much research has been done specifically on this CRSF however a research by Yazn (2012) and Lorraine (2013), does indicate it can be an influencing factor for above mentioned reasons.

O5 Service level agreements and monitoring; A service Level agreement (or SLA) is the part of a contract which defines exactly what services a service provider will provide and the required level or standard for those services. The SLA is generally part of an outsourcing or managed services agreement or can be used in facilities management agreements and other agreements for the provision of services (Cordall, 2019).

As already stated in the data privacy section, careful and diligent design of SLAs is important for a successful SaaS contractual agreement. To meet the requirements of different groups of customers cloud providers have the possibility to offer different levels of service. For example, Microsoft offers several levels of services at different prices, which includes more or less products.

Although a cloud provider might be tempted to overestimate its actual capabilities to attract more customers, for long lasting relationships, a trustful and truthful declaration of abilities and weaknesses is important. Otherwise, SLAs usually include penalties for non-compliance, which are to be avoided at all cost (Baun, Kunze, Nimis, & Tai, 2011).

Another aspect relevant to SLAs is service monitoring, in other words, managing the continuous devotion to the service level as agreed upon. Quantitative aspects such as uptime and latency can

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easily be monitored over time with little effort. Cloud providers are best advised to proactively guarantee such procedures before a customer does (Baun, Kunze, Nimis, & Tai, 2011).

E1 Regulatory environment; is about the local regulations that might affect the cloud adoption. This is a tricky one, since this specific CRSF is based a lot on the country, region and also industry so this can always play an important factor.

E2 Service Providers support; is about the support provided by the provider for adoption to the cloud. Within the research we have not found many references to this, however the research of Yeboah-Boateng & Essandoh (2014) indicates that is this is a critical factor for adoption to the cloud. Especially regarding technical and user support from the provider.

E3 Perceived industry pressure; is meant with the degree the company is affected by competitors in the markets, with the question being to what extend this affects the adoption to cloud. A Study by Hans et al. (2013) confirmed the hypothesis that competition intensity relates positively to cloud computing adoption since it increases innovation pressure. One of the reasons is that cloud computing has the potential to quicker scale and implement technological changes which can help establish new services without large investments upfront.

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4 RESULTS

The data found in the literature is compared with the results from the interviews. The results of the interviews are also examined from an architecture, governance and overall point of view. CSF's which should be focused on first, are those with a rating of 4 and higher. Thereafter, the focus should be on the CSF's, which have a point difference of 1 or larger.

4.1 Critical Success factors overall:

Figure 11 Comparison Critical success factors overall

Examining the overall results of the interviews (Figure 11), it can be concluded that in general the 3 different type of stakeholders are in agreement when it comes to view expectations. Another interesting fact is, that regulatory environment (4,7) has scored the highest overall, followed by information security (4,6) and data security (4,6). This is sensible, while there are many regulations in regard to data and privacy, which can result in high fines if not done correctly. The interviews reflected this as well, as brokers and providers indicated that they received many questions in regard to the implementation of information security and data security. Further it was observed that this

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must be built in by design and it should not affect the users, otherwise it might hurt the adoption. Although, overall information and data security have the highest score overall, there is a different understanding of importance between the broker (3,67) and the customer (5,00). However, both are still in the top 5 of most important factors with an average value of 4 or higher.

The CSF that scored the lowest, was perceived industry pressure (1,8). This factor was mentioned in many papers as a potential CSF, therefore this result is quite a surprise. However, during the interviews this was not deemed critical, nor was it noticed that this could have impact. A explanation for this could be that most of the articles where perceived industry pressure was mentioned, where written in a time when cloud started to become popular. Nowadays it has progressively become the new status-quo.

In conclusion, the CSF's with a rating of 4 and higher, are the factors which should be focused on first. Thereafter, the focus should be on the CSF's, which have a point difference of 1 or larger between broker and customer, while this might indicate a difference in expectations and thus potentially hinder the adoption.

	Most important CSF's		CSF's require extra attention
1	Regulatory environment	1	Information security
2	Information security	2	Data security
3	Data security	3	Service providers support
4	Service level agreements and monitoring	4	Relative advantage
5	Service providers support	5	

Table 6 Most important Critical Success Factors Overall

Examining the overall scores based on, total overall, total governance and total architecture, a comparison can be made between overall and governance. However, while those differences aren't exactly relevant to this research, they won't be discussed here further. The results can be found in the appendix (Annex 1: Interview data).

During the literature research a lot of CSF's have been identified. However, according to the key experts, some CSF are still missing. These missing CSF's are listed below.

Consumerization of IT

Employees want the same ease in their work as at home. In general, business solutions lag behind the consumer market when it comes to options and flexibility. This is a factor that counts from an end-user perspective.

People expect extremely fast update cycles, because of the apps they use at home are continuously updated and provided with new features. The same behavior is expected in a business application.

Realism

The attitude of accepting the SaaS solution as it is and being prepared to deal with it and integrate it into your business accordingly. Customization of SaaS is almost impossible, therefore companies need to accept the solution as it is without wanting to change a lot. Instead, they need to tweak their business processes a fragment.

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Research and solution Intent

Research and solution intent serves as a vision of the future SaaS system. It provides the detail needed to establish the current vision but allows to explore the unknown in the solution. The resulting knowledge “Can we implement the future SaaS solution and what did we learn from exploration?” provides feedback on the to-be SaaS solution and the opportunity to adapt and adopt.

Procurement Process

The procurement process overall can be critical important for companies leading up to their final purchasing decision for which SaaS service they choose.

Mindset of employees

The Mindset of the employees is very important for the Adoption. Before migrating to the new solution employees should be trained. They know the business inside out, and should be fully focused on the adoption process, so the SaaS solution can be integrated as good as possible into the business.

4.2 CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS FROM AN ARCHITECTURE POINT OF VIEW

Figure 12 Comparison Critical success factors from an architecture point of view

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From an architecture point of view for the broker (5), provider (5) as well as the customer (4,83), data security and information security are very important. This also became apparent after each interview that was done. For customers it is important that data security and information security is guaranteed in every SaaS project. Therefore, customers first check whether this is properly guaranteed in the new SaaS solution. In addition, this is reflected in every conversation that a provider has with a customer. Information to companies is their license to operate, if this is not in order then they are out of business. There are many factors which have a slow term effect, but security is one of the factors which has to be dealt with on the longer term, but its effects can be seen in a short term.

When it comes to compatibility, it can be concluded from the interviews, that this is not a very important factor to the provider (3). On the other hand, it is of importance to the customers (4), and even more to the brokers (4,67). The interviews show that the SaaS solution must be properly linked to the back end, otherwise problems will develop.

The provider (2) considers top management support less important than the customer (4) and the broker (4). The interviews show that providers think that top management support contributes very little to cloud adoption. For them support from IT management is more important. However, the customer and broker think the exact opposite. They indicate that when pushing from top management, the business is less likely to counteract during the adoption process. Therefore the application lands better in the organization. If it is forced from above, it will also be more accepted.

Considering the CSF firm size, it is much less important to the provider (1) than the broker (3,33) and the customer (3,67). Provider indicates that newer companies find it easier to deal with cloud adoption This has more to do with the sector the companies operate in, and not with the firm size. Naturally, it is important that a large organization has a good migration or implementation plan. However, the size of the company should make no difference. The customer cannot ignore the firm size, but this is not a crucial factor. The broker confirms this, stating it only affects the time invested in the SaaS project. However, it is easier for smaller companies to accept and adopt to SaaS, than it is for larger companies.

The last disagreement on CSF, from an architecture point of view is the CSF Service level agreement In comparison it is more important to the provider (5) than the customer (3,67) and broker (4). One of the explanations for this can be that the capabilities of service management are built into SaaS applications. This could make it easier to use them. In addition, it is also about how quickly you can get support during escalations of the project, which certainly has an impact on the adoption of SaaS.

In conclusion, the CSF's with a rating of 4 and higher, are the factors which should be focused on first. Thereafter, the focus should be on the CSF's, which have a point difference of 1 or larger between broker and customer, while this might indicate a difference in expectations and thus potentially hinder the adoption.

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	Most important CSF's		CSF's require extra attention
1	Information security	1	Service providers support
2	Regulatory environment	2	Relative advantage
3	Data security		
4	Compatibility		

Table 7 Most important Critical Success Factors Architecture

4.2.1 Expectations with regards to architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

Research shows that key experts disagree on how the future of architecture for cloud adoption will look. Some of them argue that, in comparison to on premise, architecture won't change when applied to cloud. And then there are key experts who indicate that architecture will become more important. The more SaaS solutions a company implements, the more complex the IT landscape will become, while everything has to be connected. Another reason is, architecture is increasing its focus on risk and cyber security. Cloud architecture can only succeed, when one knows what people are doing on the work floor. In addition it is important to remain focused on the way the cloud landscape changes.

“SaaS solutions can be compared to a group of small islands. Make the islands work as if they are one big country. To do this, architecture becomes even more important in a SaaS landscape, otherwise it would be very difficult to manage properly (Robijns, 2020).”

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4.3 CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS FROM A GOVERNANCE POINT OF VIEW

Figure 13 Comparison Critical success factors from a governance point of view

Examining the results of the interviews (figure 13), it can be concluded that the 3 parties are on average in agreeance on what is important and what is not. However there are some interesting differences. Overall the information security and data security score best. Both score very well from a customer perspective (4,4 & 4,4). This is understandable, while data and information security is a top priority for many companies, especially considering the regulations and fines linked to these. Interesting however is that from a broker perspective (3,67 & 3,33) these are less important. One of the possible reasons, which was extracted from the interviews, is that while brokers do find information and data security important, especially from an architecture point of view, both are seen as something complex and difficult which might hinder the speed of implementation, when viewed from a governance context. Therefore brokers do not see it as a factor relevant for the adoption or success of the project.

The CSF service level agreements and monitoring can be assigned to the third place of overall importance in governance. Interesting enough, this CSF has a lower score from the broker perspective (4) than from the customer perspective (4,5). According this research, brokers are more

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interested in the project, and the delivery of the cloud project, including adoption. Therefore they find SLA's only relevant after the ending of the project. Customers on the other hand perceive this to be important during the project. For example they want clear agreements beforehand and during the cloud implementation. Without these, the whole cloud adoption might be negatively impacted when something goes wrong. Interesting enough, the CSF server provider support scores the highest for Brokers (5). Brokers feel the need to support their customers. Therefore they should be there every step of the way in order to ensure the success of the cloud implementation. The customer (4,17) agrees that customer service support is important, however they do not find this as important as the broker. This is mainly because, they see SaaS as something they should be able to handle themselves. However, this creates a big risk when it comes to cloud adoption. When an issue appears and the customer tries to solve it themselves, instead of reaching out to the broker or cloud supplier, can result in delays and/or negatively impact the cloud and the adoption process for the users.

Focusing on compatibility, it can be noted that it has the second highest rating from a broker perspective (4,67), while from the perspective of the provider (3) and the customer (2,67) it has a lower priority. The same can be said for complexity. From the customer perspective this is mostly seen as an architecture question than a governance question. It has to work with the on premise / other SaaS applications. The cloud can also be seen as a new silos, switching from one cloud to another is not as easy as it seems. However, a good governance could support this.

The last big difference which has been identified is trialability. The brokers find this important (4,33), especially when moving from on premise to SaaS. When users try out the new SaaS, before implementation, they will get used to the new settings. If this is a success, it will support the adoption to cloud. From a governance customer perspective (2,33), this is not always easy. Due to regulations, laws, and internal processes it is not always possible to sample a new SaaS. In addition, they argue that it is more of an architectural challenge than a governance challenge.

In conclusion, the CSF's with a rating of 4 and higher, are the factors which should be focused on first. Thereafter, the focus should be on the CSF's, which have a point difference of 1 or larger between broker and customer, while this might indicate a difference in expectations and thus potentially hinder the adoption (Table 8).

	Most important CSF's		CSF's require extra attention
1	Data security	1	Compatibility
2	Information security	2	Complexity
3	Service level agreements and monitoring	3	Trialability
4	Service providers support	4	Relative advantage
5	Regulatory environment	5	Information security
6	IT managers support	6	Data security
7	Top management support		

Table 8 Most important Critical Success Factors Governance

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4.3.1 Expectations with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption.

Looking at the what the future could potentially hold with regards to governance in cloud and the cloud adoption, the experts in general have the same expectations. This is quite interesting, as most of them see the same challenges and opportunities in the future. What they expect is that governance will get an more important role especially how to handle data and local laws and regulations. Particularly the laws and regulations, is something they expect to be more challenging in the future and a lot to learn right now. One of the opportunities they see is that cloud becomes more business as usual and more complex solutions being moved to the cloud. Resulting in more and more best practices being created and that existing frameworks will be enriched with these best practices.

5 CONCLUSION

What are identified critical success factors for cloud adoption?

Reviewing the findings of this research, it can be concluded that almost all CSF's, which have been identified in literature, have importance (rating 2.5 or higher), except for perceived industry pressure. It is not surprising that cloud adoption requires many factors. A substantial amount of research has been done into defining it's CSF's; and the process of adopting to cloud is complex. Thus can be stated with reasonable assurance that following CSF's play a significant role in cloud adoption:

Regulatory environment	Top management support
Information security	Technological readiness
Data security	Relative advantage
Service level agreements and monitoring	Cost
Service providers support	Firm size
Compatibility	Complexity
Trialability	Perceived industry pressure
IT managers support	

Table 9 identified critical success factors

It can be considered, that these factors play a significant role in cloud adoption. Therefore, they should be used as a guideline, to identify important factors in every cloud adoption case.

Beside these CSF's, there are the "missing" CSF's which have been identified by the key experts. These are:

Consumerization of IT	Procurement Process
Realism	Mindset employees
Research and solution Intent	

Table 10 Missing CSF's

The TOE Framework is used to frame the CSF's, research point out that the CSF's that need extra attention are from a technological context influencing a firm adoption decisions. From architecture point of view it is 50 percent of the CSF's that are from a technological point of view. For overall it is 75 percent and from an governance point of view it is even 100 percent of the CSF's that are from a technological point of view. According to Baker (2011) organizations must carefully consider the type of organizational changes that will be created by adopting a new solution. Some solutions will have a dramatic impact on the firm and the industry in which it competes, while others will have a relatively small impact. This makes it even more important to pay extra attention to these critical success factors.

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Conclusion

How can architectural models support cloud adoption?

“SaaS solutions can be compared to a group of small islands. Make the islands work as if they are one big country. To do this, architecture becomes even more important in a SaaS landscape, otherwise it would be very difficult to manage properly (Robijns, 2020).”

The CSF's can be linked to different phases of the studied Architecture Frameworks TOGAF and the Adaptive cloud Enterprise Framework. Therefore, both frameworks are suitable for cloud adoption. Still organisations need to tailor their enterprise architecture framework that suits their specific needs.

The Zachman framework only provides the architecture taxonomy and does not provide any concrete enterprise architecture guidelines and/or methods. DYA describes how to embed architecture within an organization and offers descriptions of processes. Therefore, none of the CSF's can be linked to both frameworks and means these frameworks are less suitable for cloud adoption.

How does IT cloud governance models support cloud adoption?

It is not easy to link the identified CSF's directly to a framework. They all support cloud adoption in their own way, however it really depends on what the focus is. For example, COBIT can help with the adoption of the cloud, so business gets their value and help them assess many security or value issues. ISO 27000 and ISAE 3402 are very good for making risks transparent and putting focus on security. All governance models can support in some way, depending on the governance model the organization is using at the moment. Besides the governance model, factors which are important for the specific organization should be leading in the decision on which governance model will be used. So we can conclude that there is not yet one framework that covers all aspects. COBIT 2019 is making a good start with it, with the creation of a focus area focusing on cloud computing but it does not solve everything yet. But as indicated by the experts interviews, there expectation is that in the future cloud and cloud governance will business as usual and then the frameworks will be adopted.

What are the critical success factors of adoption to a Public cloud computing (SaaS) from an IT governance and Enterprise architecture point of view?

The most important CSF's from an overall perspective, architecture perspective and governance perspective are information security, data security, and regulatory environment. Companies need to focus on these CSF's to increase the chance of successful cloud adoption, to successfully implement their specific SaaS solutions and to get the maximal profit from their investments.

Research has also revealed, that both data security and information security, are regarded from three points of view (broker, provider, and customer) as the CFS's that require extra attention. These findings might indicate a difference in expectations and thus potentially hinder cloud adoption. Therefore, it is very important that both CFS's are guaranteed during the adoption process.

5.1 RECOMMENDATION

The results of this research serves as a valuable guide for management, cloud broker and cloud provider. As observed in the results, a lot of research has to be done to specific areas of cloud adoption. However, an overall review which could be used as a starting point, was lacking. Our research provides a list with CSF's, which are important in a specific cloud adoption case. The recommendation is, for every new project where cloud adoption is part of, to take our identified CSF's as starting point and then in collaboration with all stakeholders assess which one are most important and plan accordingly. Based on our research results we recommend to especially focus on those CSF's which have the highest differentiation in importance, which are: Service providers support, relative advantage, data security, information security, compatibility, complexity, Trialability and Service providers support.

6 REFLECTION

The added value of the duo thesis is that we followed different programs within the master study. Therefore, the ideal opportunity was provided to us to look at the problem statement from different perspectives and backgrounds.

Over time, multiple sessions were required to change the design and methodology of the research in order to stay focused on the study objective “What are the critical success factors for cloud adoption from an architecture and governance point of view?”. While the overall scope was clear for our research, some changes were made to get to the outcome of the thesis.

6.1 POINTS OF REFLECTION

Literature

The intention of the literature research was to get a clear overview of what the CSF's for cloud adoption are. Much research has been done, in different countries and industries, on CFS's for cloud adoption. There were many CFS's for cloud adoption and strongly focused on just one industry. The importance of these CSF's was varying strongly in the different articles (and in some cases were contradicting).

Interviews

From the beginning, interviews and questionnaires were considered as a part of our research. Due to the complexity of the research, it was considered to have only semi-structured interviews. In addition, originally it was intended to have three interviews per target group focused on companies based in the Netherlands. Due to the governmental restrictions based on COVID-19, hurdles were experienced with getting appointments for interviews. Therefore, it was only possible to conduct one interview for the target group provider. During the interviews, it was observed that cloud adoption is a hot topic in every company and were looking for the "right" way to apply cloud adoption.

6.2 FURTHER RESEARCH

From this research a few proposals can be made for further research. As described in the previous section, the research focuses on companies based in the Netherlands. Further research in other countries is recommended on the effect of the CSF's of adoption process.

Furthermore, findings from our research reveals that the CSF's can be applied in various governance and architecture frameworks. Future research can reveal how exactly these CSF's should be integrated in a specific architecture or governance framework. Or future research could be done by means of a correlation matrix of what impact or interdependencies the different CSF's have with each other.

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Annex 1: Interview data

CSF	Total Overall	Total Governance	Total Architecture
Regulatory environment	4,70	4,30	4,90
Information Security	4,60	4,40	4,90
Data Security	4,60	4,50	4,80
Service level agreements and monitoring	4,20	4,40	3,90
Service Providers support	4,10	4,40	3,90
Compatibility	3,90	3,00	4,10
Trialability	3,90	3,10	3,80
IT managers Support	3,90	4,20	3,90
Top Management Support	3,80	4,10	3,80
Technological Readiness	3,80	3,80	3,90
Relative advantage	3,60	3,40	3,70
Cost	3,40	3,00	3,30
Firm Size	3,30	3,00	3,30
Complexity	3,00	2,40	3,80
Perceived industry pressure	1,80	2,30	1,80

Table 11 Ratings from interviews

Figure 14 Comparison averages

Figure 15 Comparison Overall

Governance

Figure 16 Comparison Governance

Architecture

Figure 17 Comparison Architecture

Annex 2: Interview questions

ID Question

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS?
2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution?
3. What is your experience with cloud adoption?
4. What went well, what were pitfalls?

5 From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important and please explain why

	Overall	IT Governance	Architecture
5.1 Information Security			
5.2 Data Security			
5.3 Cost			
5.4 Relative advantage			
5.5 Complexity			
5.6 Compatibility			
5.7 Trialability			
5.8 Top Management Support			
5.9 Technological Readiness			
5.10 Firm Size			
5.11 IT managers Support			
5.12 SLA's and monitoring			
5.13 Regulatory environment			
5.14 Service Providers support			
5.15 Perceived industry pressure			

6. Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

7. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

8. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption?

Annex 3: Interview elaborations

Company: Microsoft Dublin.

Function: Cloud solution architect.

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS

Cloud is een heel praktisch iets, je ontzorgt er klanten makkelijk mee. Ik geloof heel erg in het cloud hybride model. Men kan namelijk niet altijd alles in de Cloud zetten, dit vanwege latency en regulations of technische beperkingen. Maar hij ziet zeker een groei in de vraag naar SaaS.

De stap naar SAAS is heel erg interessant. Omdat voor klanten heel makkelijk is, maar het zal niet voor iedereen werken (niet 100% SaaS).

2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution

De een is wat beter in, als de andere. Bij overheden en zorginstellingen zitten met budgetten. Ziet dat er Budget fear is bij klanten, bang dat het snel teveel gaat kosten en de klanten zien daardoor niet het totale plaatje. Vaak wordt gezegd dat Cloud duur is, als je 1 op 1 zaken gaat overzetten dan is het inderdaad niet voordelig. Klanten moeten kijken waar wel winst op gehaald kan worden. Dingen kunnen als het anders inricht wordt ook goedkoper zijn. Voor de klant een voordeel, voor de leverancier natuurlijk minder aangezien ze hier dan ook minder op gaan verdienen.

Daarnaast is manageability en security ook een heel groot voordeel van SaaS. Men zit altijd op de laatste versie van de software. Klanten hoeven niet eens in de zoveel jaar een grote migratie van hun software pakket uit te voeren omdat men te ver achterligt met de versie van de software. Updates en support gaat tevens ook veel sneller met SaaS, de leverancier hoeft namelijk maar een versie bij te houden en te ondersteunen in plaats van diverse versies. Adoptie van nieuwe technieken gaat gemakkelijker omdat het platform constant geupdate wordt waardoor men telkens de nieuwste tools en technieken voor handen heeft. Dit hadden klanten niet gehad als men on-premises op een versie was blijven draaien. Klanten merken dan ook dat ze hiermee veel meer slachtkracht binnen in de eigen organisatie krijgen. Als er iets gewijzigd dient te worden aan de software is het maar een klein iets wat minder impact heeft op de gehele dienstverlening.

Versioning kan ook hinder zijn. Door modern te gaan denken, kwamen de voordelen voor Cloud. Als er iets vervangen moet worden is het makkelijk (scalability). Bij on-premises zit je vast aan je eigen cluster. Updates and features gaan heel snel bij een Cloud platform, waar je als klant niks van merkt op het gebied van beschikbaarheid.

3. What is your experience with cloud adoption? What went well, what were Pit Falls?

Went well:

Door snelle ontwikkeling worden features uitgebracht dat antwoord bied op problemen die klanten hebben waarvan ze niet weten hoe ze ermee om moeten gaan.

Door de toegevoegde waarde van het product, werd het beter geaccepteerd en wouden ze ermee verder. Door optimalisaties etc. Meer tijd voor ontwikkeling, minder tijd voor onderhoud etc.

Door inzet van SaaS kunnen klanten hun dienstverlening zoveel beter maken naar de rest van de organisatie toe. Daardoor kijken ze ook bij andere pakketten of ze hier ook niet sneller naar SaaS toe kunnen gaan om optimaal gebruik te maken van alle nieuwe methodes.

Door SaaS kunnen klanten tijd vrij maken voor hun corebusiness en niet bezig zijn met het bijhouden van de huidige systemen. Personeel kan slimmer ingezet worden voor bedrijven.

Pit Falls:

Voor personeel van leveranciers is het af en toe lastig om alle wijzigingen bij te houden. Doordat men zo snel kan ontwikkelen en nieuwe zaken worden gereleased, ligt er ook een enorme druk op de interne organisatie om dit allemaal bij te houden. Het komt wel eens voor dat klanten vragen stellen over nieuwe features waar men zelf geen idee van had dat dit al gereleased was.

Ervaring van een klant is dat ze zelf alles willen uitzoeken. Bij een Cloud project liepen ze tegen problemen aan maar ze wilden het perse zelf oplossen en daardoor ook niet delen wat het probleem is. Er was te weinig communicatie met leverancier en eindgebruikers, wat impact heeft op de adoptie van het product. Daarom dient een organisatie eindgebruiker gelijk in het begin van het proces mee te nemen. Doet men dit niet dan heeft het ook impact heeft op toekomstige projecten. Willen dit probleem als leverancier graag tackelen zijn alleen nog niet erover uit hoe ze dit gaan doen.

4. From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important

		Overall	IT Governance	Architecture	Explain why
5.1	Information Security	5	5	5	Klanten vinden dit super belangrijk dat dit gewaarborgd is. Dit komt in elk gesprek dat hij met klanten heeft terug dat security gewaarborgd moet zijn.
5.2	Data Security	5	5	5	Klanten vinden dit super belangrijk dat dit gewaarborgd is. Dit komt in elk gesprek dat hij met klanten heeft terug dat security gewaarborgd moet zijn.
5.3	Cost	3	3	3	De ene klant vindt het belangrijker dan de andere klant, maar het wordt altijd wel in overweging genomen.
5.4	Relative advantage	4	4	4	Veel klanten zien dat het overgaan naar de Cloud een voordeel geeft ten opzichten van niet overgaan naar de Cloud. Scalability & newest technology.
5.5	Complexity	4	4	4	Het is heel belangrijk voor ze dat ze de nieuwe technologie begrijpen en hoe ze hiermee om

					dienen te gaan. Schakelen met partners om trainingen te geven en waar geen trainingen worden gegeven ziet men dat compleet de soep in kan lopen.
5.6	Compatibility	3	3	3	Voor de ene klant is het heel belangrijk dat men kan koppelen met de on-premises omgeving, de andere klant maakt het niks uit en zorgt ervoor dat ze het werkend krijgen.
5.7	Trialability	4	4	4	Merkt alleen bij kleine klanten dat ze het willen uitproberen, grotere klanten gaan het gesprek aan en als het goed klinkt geven ze aan dit gaan we gewoon doen. Als ze een trail doen dan helpt het wel bij de Cloud adoptie. Geeft rust en zekerheid om het te gaan gebruiken.
5.8	Top Management Support	2	2	2	Als het gesprekken zijn om C level gaat het over is het veilig en gaat het ons helpen. Is wel van belang maar heeft niet enorme impact.
5.9	Technological Readiness	4	4	4	Klanten vragen heel vaak, wat voor impact heeft het op trainingen, wat voor kennis hebben mijn mensen nodig. Wat voor technologisch kennis niveau dient mijn organisatie te hebben vandaar een 4.
5.10	Firm Size	1	1	1	Nieuwere bedrijven vinden het makkelijker, heeft met sector te maken en niet met organisatie omvang. Natuurlijk is het voor een grote organisatie belangrijk dat er een goed plan ligt. Maar nooit dat dit impact erop heeft gehad.
5.11	IT managers Support	5	5	5	Als de IT manager er niet achter staat dan win je nooit.
5.12	Service level agreements	5	5	5	Klanten vinden het belangrijk hoe ze hun dienstverlening kunnen waarborgen en welke

	and monitoring				handvaten de klant heeft om dat te kunnen doen.
5.13	Regulatory environment	5	5	5	Krijgen enorm veel vragen hoe het wordt gewaarborgd en hoe men voldoet aan de wet en regelgeving. Dit komt ook in ieder gesprek dat hij heeft met de klant terug.
5.14	Service Providers support	4	4	4	Bij ontzettend veel klanten wordt er gebruik gemaakt van partners om te ondersteunen bij de implementatie, met het beheer en trainen van het interne personeel van de nieuwe oplossing.
5.15	Perceived industry pressure	1	1	1	Ziet bij Healthcare dat beetje wachten is tot het eerste schaap over de dam is. Moeten eerst zien dat het veilig is en goed gaat en dan durven ze ook de stap te nemen. Eerst moet een groot ziekenhuis overstappen voordat ook andere ziekenhuizen zullen volgen. Maar niet echt dat andere bedrijven naar de Cloud gaan omdat de concurrent het doet.

5. Please explain why

Zie tabel bij vraag 4.

6. Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

Nee, zijn compleet de succesfactoren.

7. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

Het zal altijd een ontzettend integraal onderwerp zijn. Er zal altijd lokale wetgeving zijn dat Cloud adoptie kan verstoren. GDPR. Hoe je moet omgaan met data. Governance zal steeds belangrijker worden voor klanten, daarnaast komt er ook steeds meer besef over governance.

8. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

In de toekomst zal IT meer een asset zijn en niet een lasten kostenpost voor een organisatie.

Company: Detron

Function: Business Consultant

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS

Liona geeft aan dat men kan werken vanuit van elke plek. Beveiliging is ook geen issue meer, dat is verwerkt in de oplossing. Collaboration is ook een van de voordelen die met SaaS zijn gekomen. Dit was in de traditionele on-premises oplossingen minder goed mogelijk. "Het werkt gewoon een stuk gemakkelijker".

2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution

Er is een verschil tussen het technisch werkend krijgen en de gebruikers van een bedrijf op de juiste manier van de oplossing gebruik te laten maken. Het eerste krijgt men altijd wel voor elkaar maar om een oplossing goed te laten landen bij de medewerkers is de uitdaging.

Doet men dit niet goed dan gaat de mens zelf oplossingen verzinnen om toch weer zoveel als mogelijk volgens de oude manier te werken. Want verandering vindt bijna niemand fijn.

De meerwaarde van adoptie zit niet erin wat gaat het nu voor je betekenen, maar doordat met een groep ambassadeurs wordt gekeken waar gaat de meerwaarde voor alle collega's van het bedrijf zitten.

Adoptie is een manier aanleren hoe men tegen een nieuwe oplossing aan kijkt, hoe kijk je naar een proces, hoe doen we het nu, waar lopen we tegen aan. Dit wil je graag opgelost krijgen en hoe zouden we dat willen doen. Als je ze dit proces van probleem oplossen aanleert en paar keer gedaan hebt kunnen bedrijven het zelf.

3. What is your experience with cloud adoption? What went well, what were Pit Falls?

Went well:

Het aanstellen van ambassadeurs gekozen vanuit de gehele organisatie breed, alle lagen van de organisatie hier in meenemen zodat hun de nieuwe oplossing kunnen uitdragen binnen de organisatie waardoor het project slaagt. Ook wordt de directeur gevraagd om bij oplevering van een project een filmpje kort op te nemen waarmee hij uitlegt waarom men deze oplossing heeft gekozen en welke meerwaarde het gaat toevoegen voor het bedrijf zodat de oplossing beter geadopteerd wordt.

Ziet adoptie als een manier hoe men het product / oplossing op de juiste manier kan laten landen binnen een organisatie.

Pit Falls:

Als men een te groot team van ambassadeurs heeft, vooral bij grote organisaties werkte dit tegen omdat men het niet eens met elkaar kon worden. Daarnaast bestaat er geen standaard oplossing die je Overall kunt uitrollen.

Daarnaast als men met een product live gaat waarbij de gebruikers nog niet klaar waren met de adoptie van dit product zorgde ervoor enorm veel frustratie bij de eindgebruikers en heeft men maanden nodig gehad om dit recht te trekken.

4. From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important

		Overall	IT Governance	Architecture	Explain why
5.1	Information Security	3	3	5	Vind het heel belangrijk vanuit architectuur en dat alles goed beveiligd is en dat de gebruiker hier makkelijk mee kan omgaan. Maar dit is niet een punt vanuit governance waarop een project wel of niet slaagt.
5.2	Data Security	2	2	5	Vind het een randvoorwaarde maar geen succesfactor. Vandaar dat ze hier maar een 2 aan gaf. Voor management zal dit heel belangrijk zijn, de rest van de organisatie is hier totaal niet mee bezig geeft ze aan.
5.3	Cost	4	4	4	Is belangrijk op het moment dat de keuze voor een oplossing wordt gemaakt en welke organisatie wordt gekozen als partner. De meerwaarde van adoptie wordt ook gemeten in geld.
5.4	Relative advantage	5	5	5	Dit is belangrijk omdat ze hier in het hele project mee bezig zijn. Wat levert deze oplossing voor jullie als organisatie op.
5.5	Complexity	4	4	4	Hoe meer maatwerk, hoe minder toekomst bestendig. Maak gebruik

					van de oplossingen die er zijn en koppel dat slim aan elkaar.
5.6	Compatibility	5	5	5	Vind belangrijk dat het gekoppeld kan worden aan verschillende oplossingen binnen de organisatie.
5.7	Trialability	5	5	5	Mensen willen het eerst gevoeld en gezien hebben voordat ze ergens ja tegen zeggen. Dit maakt dat mensen veel sneller gaan werken met de nieuwe oplossing en makkelijker werken met deze oplossing.
5.8	Top Management Support	4	4	4	Men moet vanaf bovenaf invloed uitoefenen op de adoptie.
5.9	Technological Readiness	3	3	3	Als dat er niet is dan accepteren gebruikers de nieuwe oplossing niet en dan ben je constant aan het verdedigen waarom dit gekozen is in plaats van de oude oplossing.
5.10	Firm Size	2	2	2	Is niet spannend, heeft alleen invloed op de tijd dat je in het project moet investeren.
5.11	IT managers Support	4	4	4	Geeft aan dat de ervaring is bij starten van een versaas project het vaker voor komt dat de IT manager opstapt. IT managers moeten achter de oplossing staan.
5.12	Service level agreements and monitoring	2	2	2	Geeft aan dat SLA's tijdens het project niet spelen.
5.13	Regulatory environment	3	3	5	Het moet goed geïmplementeerd zijn in de techniek. Beleid en wetgeving moet in de techniek verwerkt zijn, maar gebruikers moeten er geen last van ondervinden. Dit heeft invloed op de adoptie. Want de oplossing moet bruikbaar zijn. Daarnaast moeten er ook geen incidenten plaats vinden met de nieuwe

					oplossing waardoor men geen vertrouwen heeft in de oplossing.
5.14	Service Providers support	5	5	5	Mensen moeten het gevoel hebben dat er altijd iemand is die ze kunnen helpen. Dat zorgt voor betere adoptie.
5.15	Perceived industry pressure	2	2	2	Merkt niet dat dit invloed heeft op adoptie.

5. Please explain why

Zie tabel bij vraag 4.

6. Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

Waar ik denk dat echt een stukje succes factor zit is de datamigratie die klaar moet zijn voordat de gebruikers getraind worden en het ambassadeursteam. Ze moeten echt de bedrijfsprocessen kennen en vrijgemaakt worden om aandacht te geven aan het adoptietraject.

7. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

Geen enkel project wordt gestart zonder dat men aan adoptie denkt. Dit wordt dan ook gekoppeld aan de missie en strategie van het bedrijf en bij behorende wet en regelgeving.

8. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

Het is belangrijk dat constant vooruit wordt gekeken op er nog gaat komen. Want ga je niet verder in de ontwikkeling dan stopt het van zelf.

Company: APG

Function: Business Consultant

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS

Cloud is een goede ontwikkeling want hardware is niet onze core business. Cloud wordt langzamerhand een commodity, waarbij data heel erg belangrijk is. Daardoor is voor APG de private Cloud heel erg interessant. Maar voor minder kritische zaken is SaaS heel goed alternatief en wordt daardoor ook steeds meer gebruikt. Bijvoorbeeld Microsoft 365.

Als je van alles zelf naar SaaS gaat overzetten is er een grote kans dat je alles probeert te customizen. Regressie testen is volgens Dave heel erg belangrijk

Als men een SaaS oplossing afneemt dan heeft men geen last meer van updates. Dus dat spreekt zich voor om over te stappen naar SaaS. Daarbij moet men wel weer rekening houden als het geüpdate wordt automatisch ook nog met de rest van de complexe omgeving moet werken.

2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution

Dave geeft aan dat hij dit niet in het begin van het project terug ziet. Maar later wel als echt het besluit genomen is wordt er ook gekeken naar adoptie van de oplossing.

3. What is your experience with cloud adoption? What went well, what were Pit Falls?

Went well:

Bij inzetten van nieuwe SaaS oplossing is er begeleiding nodig. Bij APG werd ingezet met werkplek buddies zodat ze elkaar konden helpen bij de nieuwe oplossing waardoor het adoptie proces gemakkelijker ging.

Pit Falls:

Technische afstemming tussen interne landschap en externe landschap is lastig en wordt vaker onderschat. De belemmeringen van de interne infrastructuur het grootste struikelblok vormen voor adoptie van Cloud.

4. From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important

		Overall	IT Governance	Architecture	Explain why
5.1	Information Security	5	4	5	data is heel belangrijk is de core business
5.2	Data Security	5	4	5	data is heel belangrijk is de core business
5.3	Cost	4	2	4	APG moet heel transparant zijn over kosten die ze maken en daardoor verantwoord worden als ze

					naar de Cloud gaan dat dit een kosten besparing is.
5.4	Relative advantage	2	1	2	Cloud is gewoon een commodity, vandaar dat het niet relative advantage oplevert.
5.5	Complexity	3	1	3	De nieuwe SaaS oplossing moet niet moeilijker zijn als on premise
5.6	Compatibility	4	1	4	Oplossing moet goed kunnen koppelen met de intern landschap.
5.7	Trialability	3	1	3	Vindt vooral belangrijk in het begin stadium dat men een oplossing kan uitproberen.
5.8	Top Management Support	4	4	4	Is essentieel dat top management achter de oplossing staat.
5.9	Technological Readiness	4	5	4	Anders klagen de interne mensen dat het niet werkt, dus is belangrijk.
5.10	Firm Size	4	1	4	hoe groter het bedrijf hoe meer meningen er zijn, dus belangrijk dat je iedereen mee hebt
5.11	IT managers Support	1	1	1	hebben niet zo veel te willen. Daarnaast worden IT afdelingen steeds kleiner, veel minder belangrijk.
5.12	Service level agreements and monitoring	5	5	5	zodra je iets buiten de deur zet, kan het snel fout gaan. Er dient strakke afspraken gemaakt te worden met de leverancier.
5.13	Regulatory environment	5	3	5	APG moeten aan de wet en regelgeving voldoen. Belangrijk dat de oplossing dit ook waarborgt. Als ze er niet aan voldoen krijgen ze flinke tik op de vingers.
5.14	Service Providers support	4	5	4	Heel belangrijk tijdens het project. Er moet goede support zijn, want als dit er niet is dan gaat de adoptie down the drain.

5.15	Perceived industry pressure	1	1	1	Het moet toegevoegde waarde hebben, niet om het te doen, omdat iemand anders het doet. De oplossingen heb je al, of het on premise is of in de cloud maakt dan niet zo veel uit.
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5. Please explain why

Zie tabel bij vraag 4.

6. Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

Nee.

7. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

Steeds meer adoptie, er zullen van daar uit best practices komen en dit zal weer verwerkt worden in de bestaande governance frameworks

8. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

Denkt dat er op architectuur niks veranderd. Blijft het als een commodity zien. Of het nu Cloud is of on-premises architectuur blijft het zelfde. Architectuur komt wel steeds meer focus op it risk en cyber security.

Company: APG

Function: Enterprise Architect

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS

Er zijn twee soorten Cloud-gebruik: SaaS/ PaaS en de rest. Het verschil zit hem in wie verantwoordelijk is voor de inrichting (en dus, beveiliging, monitoring, continuatie, risk & control, etc.). Bij SaaS/ PaaS is de aanbieder dat. Bij de rest (IaaS/PaaS) ben je dat zelf als organisatie. SaaS/ PaaS is architectonisch niet heel interessant. Het meeste is geen onderdeel van je eigen architectuur, dus daar bemoei je je niet mee (wel beoordelen bij aanschaf en zo). Bij IaaS/PaaS verandert er niet zo veel, je bent nog steeds verantwoordelijk voor bijna alles wat relevant is. Als men een onveilige omgeving inricht in Azure, ben jij aansprakelijk, niet Microsoft, zeg maar.

Wij hebben een voorkeur voor het gebruik van PaaS/SaaS als het kan (het kan niet altijd), omdat SaaS een daadwerkelijke vermindering van de complexiteit van ons landschap is. Maar in het algemeen kun je stellen dat we Cloud en on-premises beschouwen als 'equal citizens'. Het is niet Cloud-first, maar eigen bedrijf-first.

Verder ziet Gerben Cloud, naast de voordelen van SaaS/ PaaS, vooral een voordeel hebben ten aanzien van 'snelle schaalbaarheid' en 'beschikbaarheid innovatieve platformen/services'. Beide zijn aspecten die on-premises veel moeilijker te realiseren zijn. Kostenvoordeel verwacht Gerben niet.

SaaS heeft als voordeel voor leveranciers dat ze maar een stack hoeven te onderhouden. Het voordeel is dus verticale integratie voor leveranciers.

Daarnaast heeft SaaS wel altijd integratie met je on-premises omgeving, hierdoor is SaaS nooit volledig SaaS.

Bij SaaS is het van levensbelang dat de SaaS applicatie goed kan koppelen. In de toekomst hebben ze misschien wel 30 SaaS providers, maar allemaal hebben ze een zekere mate van een combinatie nodig van de data die niet alleen correct moet zijn maar ook up-to-date en direct beschikbaar. Onderschat niet de coherentie problemen die je gaat krijgen in een maximaal versaad landschap. Gerben ziet dat dit voor heel veel kleine bedrijven als een non-issue want zij kunnen meestal hun helen stack bij dezelfde SaaS provider onderbrengen, waardoor dit probleem niet optreedt.

2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution

Bij elk project waar men naar Cloud migreert wordt er over Cloud adoptie nagedacht.

3. What is your experience with cloud adoption? What went well, what were Pit Falls?

Went well:

Pit Falls:

Naarmate de integratie van alle verschillende architecturen via de landschappen van de bedrijven een stevigere vorm gaat aannemen kun je verwachten dat we op een iets hoger niveau dezelfde vraagstukken terug gaan krijgen dat men ook bij een on-premises omgeving had. Gerben vergelijkt het met het fenomeen dat men zag in de jaren 60 binnen een computer, jaren 80 toen de computers in een netwerk begon te zitten tussen computers en hij ziet dit straks tussen SaaS omgevingen. Dan moet je vanuit architectuur kijken hoe wil je hier mee omgaan en waar moet je op letten. Letten op eigen flexibiliteit, met een eigen common data model aan de slag. Allerlei vormen van RISK & Control inrichten. Er van alles aan doen om er maar voor te zorgen dat als men straks heel veel SaaS

leveranciers heeft en die gaan allemaal onafhankelijk van elkaar bewegen en als klant zit je daar in het midden en Overall aan vast dan kan het een onaangename wereld worden, hier moet je goed over nadenken.

4. From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important

		Overall	IT Governance	Architecture	Explain why
5.1	Information Security	5	5	5	Information is hun license to operate, is dit niet op orde dan zijn ze out of business. Er zijn allemaal zaken die trager effect hebben, maar een van de zaken die je op langer termijn moet aanpakken maar op korte termijn effect hebben is deze.
5.2	Data Security	5	5	5	Alle data is belangrijk en alle security hiervan is belangrijk.
5.3	Cost	5	4	5	Kosten is zeker belangrijk, hoe belangrijk is niet te beantwoorden. Het punt is dat alle andere eisen van een oplossing.
5.4	Relative advantage	3	3	3	Dit is voor APG minder van toepassing, ze hebben maar 8 klanten en een pensioen fonds verhuist niet verschrikkelijk makkelijk van uitvoerder. Concurrentie is een traag ding voor APG.
5.5	Complexity	4	1	4	Complexiteit is onvermijdelijk, als het bagger is wil je het niet in je landschap hebben.
5.6	Compatibility	4	1	4	Zoals al eerder aangegeven, het moet kunnen koppelen met de on-premises omgeving.
5.7	Trialability	5	1	5	Ze doen nooit iets zonder het maar uit te proberen. Niks wordt in het landschap geplaatst voordat het getest is.

5.8	Top Management Support	1	4	1	Totaal niet belangrijk vanuit architectuur, vanuit governance wel.
5.9	Technological Readiness	4	3	4	Toepassing moet even ver zijn als de on-premises oplossing.
5.10	Firm Size	4	5	4	Het hangt ervan af of het een Key systeem of een niet key systeem is of de organisatie grote van toepassing is.
5.11	IT managers Support	1	4	1	Volgens Gerben IT support gewoon de business keuze die gemaakt wordt vanuit top management.
5.12	Service level agreements and monitoring	5	5	5	Afspraken met leveranciers is hartstikke belangrijk.
5.13	Regulatory environment	5	5	5	Regel en wetgeving is ontzettend belangrijk voor een pensioen uitvoerder.
5.14	Service Providers support	2	4	2	Een van de problemen met SaaS is dat je geen leverage hebt ondanks de grote omvang van je organisatie. Maatwerk is bijna niet mogelijk. Leveranciers gaan niet zaken voor je aanpassen omdat je dit vraagt.
5.15	Perceived industry pressure	1	3	1	Niet belangrijk

5. Please explain why

Zie tabel bij vraag 4.

6. Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

Firm Ownership

Exit Strategy (zelfs onder bepaalde regelgeving wettelijk voorgeschreven)

Maar zijn dat 'succes' factoren? Ik denk het niet. Het zijn wel belangrijke kwaliteitseisen. En de vraag is: wanneer is het een succes? Als je het gebruikt? Of als je het gebruikt en het voldoet aan (ook indirecte) kwaliteitseisen? B.v. een kleine bedrijf is meestal meer geneigd om met je mee te bewegen en dat vergroot de kans op functioneel succes. Maar een groot bedrijf is i.h.a. economisch

betrouwbaarder en beter in staat om aan b.v. bepaalde eisen ten aanzien van security en risk & control te voldoen. Oppervlakkig gezien is een kleine Firm dus beter voor succes.

Wat ik er zelf als echte succesfactoren aan zou toevoegen:

- Realism.
- Research and Solution Intent (before purchase).
- Procurement Process.

7. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

Cloud is een vorm van outsourcing. Dus je krijgt outsourcingsaspecten er bij (vendor management) maar ook regulering (denk aan DNB, EU AIFMD, etc.). Ethiek gaat steeds belangrijker worden, regulatory pressure zal toenemen. Verder is het dezelfde governance. Omdat Cloud nieuw is hebben we speciale ondersteuning voor Cloud-adoptie ingericht (Cloud loket waar know how zit). Verwacht dat dat tijdelijk is en op den duur opgaat in 'business as usual' en dan is het niet meer relevant. .

8. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

Besturing: Niet anders dan on-premises. Architecture is architecture. Inhoudelijk: applicaties moeten Cloud-ready zijn willen ze in de Cloud kunnen landen. Maar eigenlijk is dat niet Cloud-specifiek want on-premises voeren we hetzelfde beleid (voor zover haalbaar). Verwachting is dat architectuur belangrijker wordt omdat het allemaal complexer wordt.

Company: Belastingdienst

Function: Product manager / diensten manager

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS

Is veel bezig met het financiële vraagstuk. Veel aandacht op portfolio sturing, het moet allemaal binnen budget van den haag passen. (Focus op applicatie landschap) zitten vast aan 80% van applicaties. Er zijn vier product managers op het gebied van hosting & integratie, end user computing, basis infrastructuur en security & tooling.

Sinds dit jaar zijn er richtlijnen binnen de belastingdienst om naar de Cloud te mogen. Interne Cloud zijn ze aan het maken. De belastingdienst is groot genoeg om eigen Cloud te maken. Er zijn geen directe reden om naar de publieke Cloud te gaan, wel zijn ze het kijken wat redenen kunnen zijn om naar de Cloud over te stappen. Financieel zou een mogelijkheid kunnen zijn.

Grootste vraag is hoe ze het juridisch gaan doen en als de verstandhouding verslechterd met de leverancier hoe halen ze de zaken terug. Belastingdienst staat heel snel in het nieuws daarom moet men voorzichtig omgaan waar men zaken onderbrengt.

Techniek is volop vertrouwen in, maar financieel moet het kloppen, nu wordt alles gekocht en SaaS is pay per use, dit is een gigantische kosten post waar men rekening mee moet houden daarnaast moet het ook veilig zijn en dient het te moeten kunnen koppelen met de backend.

Ziet heel veel voordeel van SaaS voor kleine bedrijven maar bij grote bedrijven is het een grote stap om over te stappen naar SaaS.

2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution

De afweging wordt wel continue gemaakt tussen eigen infrastructuur of dat men moet kiezen voor Cloud, hierbij wordt dan ook nagedacht over Cloud Adoptie als men de afweging maakt voor Cloud boven investeren in eigen infrastructuur. Er zit heel veel zorg op veranderen van mindset dan dat men echt bezig is met techniek, techniek klopt wel.

3. What is your experience with cloud adoption? What went well, what were Pit Falls?

Went well:

Er dient een mindshift van ontwikkelaars plaats te vinden, ze moeten ook nadenken over infrastructuur. De zorg zit momenteel niet bij de techniek maar echt bij de definitie. Legacy zit niet altijd in de applicatie of infrastructuur, maar in de mensen die zich moeten aanpassen.

Pit Falls:

De techniek was al lang er klaar voor, maar de mensen niet nog niet. Het is een andere manier van werken en medewerkers dienen zich hierop aan te passen, dit is in het verleden wel mis gegaan.

4. From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important

		Overall	IT Governance	Architecture	Explain why
5.1	Information Security	5	5	5	Is heel erg belangrijk voor de belastingdienst dat informatie veilig is.
5.2	Data Security	5	5	5	Is heel erg belangrijk voor de belastingdienst dat data veilig is.
5.3	Cost	3	2	1	Alles draait om geld bij de belastingdienst, maar als het echt nodig is dan is het geld er wel.
5.4	Relative advantage	2	1	3	Hebben een beetje concurrentie met de ODC's en de voordelen die ze er van zouden hebben maakt hun niet zoveel flexibeler, je krijgt er ook een hoop andere nadelige zaken bij cadeau. Dit speelt ook een rol en daarom staat deze lager.
5.5	Complexity	2	1	4	Het wordt niet veel complexer en hebben de kennis volledig in huis.
5.6	Compatibility	3	2	4	Vaak verzinnen ze hun eigen zaken, dit moet compatibel zijn met hun backend. Daarnaast worden ze afgedwongen om standaarden toe te passen binnen SaaS. Maar hij geeft al aan dat ze hier toch wel weer hun zaken omheen proberen te bouwen via de beschikbare api's.
5.7	Trialability	4	2	3	Belangrijk als experimenteren en als LAB omgeving. Maar het wordt wel bemoeilijkt door wet en regelgeving met aanbestedingen dat ze niet zomaar zaken kunnen testen. Voor ontwikkeling is het ideaal.

5.8	Top Management Support	5	5	5	Het is niet alleen een technisch klusje, je moet het met zen allen willen en met zen allen achter staan. Vandaar uit moet je ook je budget voor de oplossing krijgen.
5.9	Technological Readiness	2	3	3	IT is er klaar voor de rest van de business nog niet. Technische kennis is in huis en als hij niet zou oppassen dan was alles al aan de Cloud aangesloten en Cloud geworden. Daar maakt hij zich geen zorgen over.
5.10	Firm Size	3	3	3	Dit ligt eraan hoe veel je gaat ontsluiten in de Cloud. Aangezien het voorlopig kleinschalig blijft speelt het wel een rol maar niet zo grote rol.
5.11	IT managers Support	5	5	5	Dit is belangrijk binnen de belastingdienst.
5.12	Service level agreements and monitoring	2	3	1	Ze doen intern niks met service levels, interesseert ze niet zoveel. Natuurlijk wordt dit gemonitord maar ze zitten niet op te wachten om leveranciers boetes te geven.
5.13	Regulatory environment	5	5	5	Hartstikke belangrijk, ook bij keuzes voor oplossingen aanbestedingen en waar de oplossing aan dient te voldoen.
5.14	Service Providers support	3	3	3	Denkt dat dit niet echt veel nodig is, zijn filosofie over Cloud is dat je het vooral zelf moet kunnen doen en dan moet je de service provider niet nodig hebben.
5.15	Perceived industry pressure	4	4	3	Het is een push die je vanuit de industrie krijgt waardoor je zelf ook die kant op moet gaan. Zie de oplossingen van IBM en Microsoft waar ze door gedwongen worden om ook deze kant op te gaan.

5. Please explain why

Zie tabel bij vraag 4.

6 Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

Het zijn er meer dan ik zelf ooit had bedacht, dus ik mis niets in de lijst.

7 What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

Men wordt gepushed door de industrie. Het hogere management denkt dat Cloud altijd goedkoper is. Dit zorgt weer voor druk vanuit het management. Men moet daarnaast veel rekening houden met regel en wetgeving van Europa & Nederland. Ziet de toekomst vooral als een hybride cloud waarbij veel intern en kleine dingen worden overgezet naar de Cloud dit zal puur uit kosten afweging zijn.

8 What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

Verwacht niet veel verandering op dit gebied.

Company: Belastingdienst

Function: Enterprise Architect

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS

Voor de belastingdienst zijn er best wat toepassingen waar Cloud voor ingezet kan worden. Alleen doen ze nog niet verschrikkelijk veel met Cloud, dit komt mede doordat men rekening dient te houden met privacy van gegevens van burgers, bedrijven en medewerkers van de belastingdienst. Ze zijn er zeer voorzichtig mee, de apps die ze nu in de Cloud hebben ondergebracht zijn alleen publieke gegevens in ondergebracht.

Zelf het idee dat de belastingdienst meer gebruik kan maken van de Cloud maar het moet wel op een veilige manier. Ook zou een goede toepassing zijn voor applicaties die alleen benut zijn tijdens piekbelasting. De aangifte app is hier een voorbeeld van, vanaf 1 april mag men aangifte doen, helemaal na vermelding op 1 mei in het journaal en dan wordt dit enorm belast maar de rest van het jaar staan ze helemaal niks te doen. Dit is zonde van je resources. Vooral natuurlijk met de voorkant waar de gegevens worden afgevangen maar opslag van deze gegevens in de on-premises backend.

Ook is een goede usecase van Cloud dat men niet bezig hoeft te zijn met onderhoud en dat soort zaken maar dat men zich echt kan focussen op de inhoud.

2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution

Tot een paar jaar geleden mocht er niks in de Cloud, door de regelgeving kon men ook niks in de Cloud plaatsen. Sinds een jaar mag men bepaalde gegevens in de Cloud onderbrengen. Er is nu een commissie die toets of vanuit een toepassing iets in de Cloud gezet mag worden. Goede Argumentatie, welke beveiligingsmaatregelen je genomen hebt en hoe je alles geregeld hebt. Hiermee wordt getoetst of je zaken in de Cloud kunt onderbrengen. Je moet je verhaal goed voor elkaar hebben wat voldoet aan alle eisen.

3. What is your experience with cloud adoption? What went well, what were Pit Falls?

Went well:

Zijn nu het kijken voor het onderbrengen van een Tool voor Change Management om dit in een SaaS variant af te nemen. Deze tool is voor het bijhouden van changes op applicaties, op dit moment draaien er ongeveer 700 informatie systemen binnen de belastingdienst. Voor deze wijzigingen goed te kunnen doorvoeren dient changemanagement en CMDB bijgehouden te worden. Deze applicaties zijn eigenlijk niet meer nieuw als On-premises tools af te nemen maar worden allemaal aangeboden als SaaS applicaties. Dit dient weer getoetst te worden volgens het Cloud beleid wat ervoor zorgt dat de applicatie goed land binnen de organisatie.

Pit Falls:

De belastingdienst heeft ook te maken met aanbestedingen als ze iets nieuws willen aanschaffen. SaaS oplossingen hebben meestal als prijsmodel pay-per-use. Hierdoor is het ondoorzichtig wat je moet betalen. Dat is lastig met aanbestedingen waar je normaal vooraf aangeeft dit mag het kosten waardoor de oplossing uiteindelijk duurder uitvalt dan begroot. Aangezien een hoop mensen zich bemoeien met een aanbesteding, duurt het gemiddeld minimaal 2 jaar om een applicatie te kunnen onderbrengen in de Cloud.

4. From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important

		Overall	IT Governance	Architecture	Explain why
5.1	Information Security	5	5	5	Een van de belangrijkste dingen die er is, zoals ook zojuist aangegeven, Men rekening dient te houden met privacy van gegevens van burgers, bedrijven en medewerkers van de belastingdienst.
5.2	Data Security	5	5	5	Een van de belangrijkste dingen die er is, zoals ook zojuist aangegeven, Men rekening dient te houden met privacy van gegevens van burgers, bedrijven en medewerkers van de belastingdienst.
5.3	Cost	3	3	3	Aangezien het betaald wordt door belasting betalers, moeten kosten in de klauwen gehouden worden. Het mag niet te duur worden. Ook aanbestedingen begint voornamelijk met kosten. Kosten beslaan 50 % tot 70 % van de weging in een aanbesteding.
5.4	Relative advantage	3	3	3	Je doet het voor burgers en bedrijven, daardoor moet je het ook zo makkelijk mogelijk voor deze groep maken. Het heffen van belasting dient ook zo goedkoop mogelijk te zijn. Cloud zou hierbij kunnen helpen. Bijvoorbeeld door systemen die alleen worden opgeschakeld tijdens piekbelasting. Daarnaast wordt veel ontwikkeld on-premises. Maar men zou veel efficiënter kunnen ontwikkelen in de Cloud waardoor het uiteindelijk weer goedkoper kan worden. In de Cloud is gewoon

					veel meer beschikbaar op devops gebied.
5.5	Complexity	4	2	4	Verwacht dat uiteindelijk de complexiteit minder wordt. Als je zaken in de Cloud afneemt dan worden de koppelingen die je moet onderhouden onderling minder.
5.6	Compatibility	4	2	4	Is belangrijk dat men koppeling moet kunnen maken met on-premises omgeving. Een SaaS applicatie staat nooit op zich.
5.7	Trialability	2	2	2	Het is belangrijk alleen door aanbestedingen is het altijd lastig. Want als je een product uitprobeert voor aanbesteden dan is het onwillige concurrentie. Dit zal dus geen succesfactor zijn ondanks dat hij aangeeft wel belangrijk vindt.
5.8	Top Management Support	5	5	5	Heel belangrijk, er wordt veel meer vanaf boven af gestuurd dus het is belangrijk dat top management support er is.
5.9	Technological Readiness	3	3	3	We lopen altijd een beetje achter op de markt. Dit heeft te maken dat stabiliteit heel belangrijk is.
5.10	Firm Size	4	4	4	Redelijk belangrijk, spelen altijd op zekerheid. Er zijn eisen aan een bedrijf gesteld als leverancier. Grote organisaties zoals de belastingdienst zijn logger. Je moet door een heleboel hoepeltjes heen springen voordat je het voor elkaar hebt.
5.11	IT managers Support	5	5	5	Die heb je ook hard nodig. Is weer een van die hoepeltjes waar je doorheen moet springen.
5.12	Service level agreements and monitoring	4	4	4	Vindt dit ook heel erg belangrijk dat er goede SLA's zijn met de leveranciers.

5.13	Regulatory environment	5	5	5	Zeer belangrijk omdat de belastingdienst aan behoorlijk wat regels en wetgeving houden.
5.14	Service Providers support	4	4	4	Belangrijk dat er support is vanuit de leverancier voor de belastingdienst.
5.15	Perceived industry pressure	1	1	1	Is niet van toepassing op de belasting dienst.

5. Please explain why

Zie tabel bij vraag 4.

6. Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

Kan er zo geen een bij verzinnen, dus wat mijn betreft is de lijst wel compleet.

7. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

Hier is nog veel te leren. Leren omgaan met regelgeving, dit is waar ze nu mee bezig zijn. Leren hoe pas je governance toe en hoe ga je er concreet mee om. Ook hoe controleer je de zaken die je in de Cloud hebt gezet. Blijft super belangrijk stidat gegevens van burgers en bedrijven niet gestolen zullen worden.

8. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

Architectuur slaagt alleen door middel van dat je weet waar de mensen op de werkvloer mee bezig zijn. Ziet dat veel architecten nu alleen maar document zijn het reviewen, dit komt Cloud adoptie ook niet ten goede. Dit zal in de toekomst ook alleen nog maar belangrijker worden.

Company: Mercedes Benz

Function: CIO

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS

Thinks that any company migrating their on premises to SaaS is not so different. Of course the amount of processes is in each company different, but from a general perspective, it is an strategic decision and topic at the end. We already doing it moving systems to SaaS. From an strategic point of view we are deciding for Cloud solutions.

Strategic wise for all systems which are not contributing to the core of our organization, why should I do that on my own. If you don't put those solutions in the Cloud it is always an struggle to the organization. You need to do server upgrade, server patching, application patching and all these kind of stuff which is not the core functionality or core business of us in IT from an governance perspective now to spend a lot of time on that. So why should I not give this time, ask other service providers completely outside the organization that manage infrastructure wise and software wise completely outside.

Would we do in the future, strategic wise, for example our CRM completely as an managed externally without internally work on, he doubts because we always will have tasks to fore fill where quickly changes needs to be done. You just don't want that it is completely out of control. Because at the end when noting is not working, IT needs to make it work. When you have software completely outsourced and an agent needs to call an external number. They will not understand it and then you lose a lot of flexibility to do small changes on our own. There he would see more the strategic direction for core business more in the Cloud then an completed outsourced solutions (SaaS). But at the end SaaS doesn't need to be more expensive then the inhouse solution. There he sees that SaaS is getting cheaper over time.

2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution

To an certain extend yes, but not visible enough and are we consistently doing it, no. But what will be clear for moving to cloud there is a lot of change management needed what we are currently not doing enough. Also we need to look for who is effected by the change that is also a thing we don't do constantly enough. But in the end the solution is working and that is good.

3. What is your experience with cloud adoption? What went well, what were Pit Falls?

Went well:

With a project moving to the Cloud, a lot colleges where having stress maintaining the inhouse solution. He reduced this stress for his colleagues by moving the solution to a SaaS variant. This reduced stress and work, they can now more focus on other thing.

Pit Falls:

Like said in the previous question, there is a lot of change management needed what we are currently not doing enough. Also we need to look for who is effected by the change that is also a thing we don't do constantly enough.

4. From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important

		Overall	IT Governance	Architecture	Explain why
5.1	Information Security	5	5	5	Without doubt very important for Daimler.
5.2	Data Security	5	5	5	Without doubt very important for Daimler.
5.3	Cost	2	2	3	The cost factor is over estimated because we only take in account we go to Cloud, we pay a monthly fee and in the end that is more then it cost today. That is what you normally get when you talk to people about cloud. Then I ask what do you consider in the calculation? Because the profile of the employees is changing. There might be ten that I don't need for certain disciplines anymore and I need them to speed up somewhere else. That cost you need to calculate against it.
5.4	Relative advantage	4	4	4	
5.5	Complexity	1	1	5	The whole infrastructure part is gone, this should be for the organization not important. For architecture this is important.
5.6	Compatibility	4	4	4	Needs to be compatible with our backend.
5.7	Triability	4	4	4	It is difficult, because I have to manage it with a partner from a cloud solution so that is important and it also have to work. Doesn't see here differences from on-premises to Cloud.

5.8	Top Management Support	5	5	5	Super important
5.9	Technological Readiness	4	4	4	It's quite important.
5.10	Firm Size	3	1	3	We cannot ignore firm size but it is also not super important.
5.11	IT managers Support	5	5	5	Super important. 80% of it is change management, 20% of it is work.
5.12	Service level agreements and monitoring	4	5	4	It is important, generally it is part of the solution and mandatory. The software is running in a different data center. It needs to perform and therefore you need a set of KPI's so measure this. For Governance this is even more important.
5.13	Regulatory environment	4	2	4	It is also important.
5.14	Service Providers support	4	4	4	
5.15	Perceived industry pressure	1	4	1	Doesn't give shit about pressure but in the documentation of the company it says: "We need to be like amazon, Netflix, spotify" Their natural reaction is but we are not amazon. Other statements in documentation is: "This is so cool what amazon is doing, we need to be like them". But it is more how they handle certain things. It is mindset in the end. For governance, it is more important. It is more emotional then regular.

5. Please explain why

Zie tabel bij vraag 4.

6. Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

I think that Mindset of the employees is very important for the Adoption.

7. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

Cloud will become cheaper, which is logical because it comes with a lot of technology. It is scaling effect. How more customers, how cheaper they can make it. For now there is for what he knows a lot of overcapacity in the datacenters of suppliers. These overhead will become smaller because they will have more customers. He doesn't know if there will be a "Super Cloud" where all the services are hosted. Because it will take a lot of time before changes will get processed and that kind of stuff. So a lot of things will change. The accessibility will be much higher. It will also mean that more complex solutions can move easier to the Cloud in the future because suppliers that have on-premises solutions need to move to cloud technology in the future but will not ignore the customer that they still have in on-premises solutions. So they will also offer migration solutions.

The perceived pressure will reach it maximum. Because you will get challenged others can do it, why not we? The longer you don't move, the higher the pressure will be. Also believes that not everything can run in the Cloud. Also on management they need to work pro-actively on strategies how do we move to this directions and get the resistance out of the organization.

8. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

What we already did, how do you do interfacing. There are still a lot of classical things we do. The complete datacenter will change from an architecture point of view. Also there bigger changes will come.

Company: True

Function: Cloud Architect

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS

Technisch gezien laat SaaS het beheer volledig bij de leverancier zitten, als broker wil je eigenlijk niet bezig zijn met het onderhouden van connectoren en dat soort zaken. De meeste partijen bieden tegenwoordig wel een SaaS variant aan, dus op het maintenance gebied ben ik zeker een voorstander ervan. Financieel gezien, wilt men als broker zolang mogelijk nog aanhouden om paar servers te verkopen. De meeste brokers hebben namelijk geïnvesteerd in een datacenter en dat dient nog altijd terugverdiend te worden. Samengevat Cloud kost meer maar de complexiteit neemt af. Merkt wel dat er een hele move plaatst vindt van traditioneel Citrix en ander vergelijkbaar werkplek concepten naar een SaaS / Webbased werkplek concept. Hier hebben ze een soort portal voor Canvas365 die deze web based SaaS diensten samen bundelt en vanuit een portaal aanbiedt.

2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution.

Je ziet dat de focus steeds meer gaat naar SaaS gaat, dit wordt makkelijker voor de mensen, maar je merkt wel dat vaak de initiële aftrap vanuit de applicatie komt. Zodra de klant een SaaS product heeft draaien en de eenvoud en maintenance free van het product merkt gaat men meestal proberen alles te versaaen.

3. What is your experience with cloud adoption? What went well, what were Pit Falls?

Went well:

True geeft zelf geen trainingen maar hebben vanuit de holding een bedrijf wat onder de BroadHorizon Groep valt, Brainwave. Zij zijn helemaal gespecialiseerd op het geven van trainingen en adoptie van een nieuwe werkplek. Als zij de migratie doen wordt parallel hiervan Brainwave ingeschakeld. Je ziet ook vaak dat de klant er behoefte aan heeft en dat de oplossing veel beter landt en veel sneller met de SaaS oplossing kunnen werken.

Pit Falls:

Hoe ga je om met lokale bronnen en hoe krijg je alles gekoppeld. Als er een applicatie die naar lokale file server moet praten zorgt dit voor problemen met ontsluiting en hierdoor werkt het product niet goed wat weer niet goed is voor de adoptie. Dus heeft vooral als Architect moeite met hoe krijg je alles goed aan elkaar gekoppeld. Integratie met oude en nieuwe software.

4. From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important

		Overall	IT Governance	Architecture	Explain why
5.1	Information Security	5	5	5	Is heel belangrijk voor True
5.2	Data Security	5	5	5	Is heel belangrijk voor True

5.3	Cost	3	3	3	Als de oplossing veel geld kost maar de beveiliging is wel veel beter dan is dit het waard en dan worden meestal ook wel deze kosten gemaakt.
5.4	Relative advantage	4	4	4	Het maakt je leven vanuit technisch oogpunt een stuk gemakkelijker, on-premises tegenover SaaS. Je hoeft geen onderhoud meer uit te voeren op de applicatie.
5.5	Complexity	3	3	3	Vindt complexiteit minder belangrijk, als het maar kan koppelen met de back-end.
5.6	Compatibility	5	5	5	Vindt het belangrijk dat de SaaS applicatie goed gekoppeld kan worden aan de back-end, anders zorgt dit voor problemen met de adoptie.
5.7	Trialability	4	4	4	Als de gehele organisatie wordt geraakt door de wijziging van on-premises naar SaaS dan merk je dat een klant zeker behoefte heeft om de oplossing uit te kunnen proberen. Hierdoor is de klant beter voorbereid en gaat het adoptie proces veel gemakkelijker. Geeft meer rust in de organisatie.
5.8	Top Management Support	4	4	4	Als er vanuit directie gepushed is men minder geneigd om tegengas te geven tijdens het adoptie proces en daardoor land de applicatie beter in de organisatie. Als het meer geforceerd wordt, wordt het ook meer geaccepteerd.
5.9	Technological Readiness	4	4	4	Het moet goed voorbereid zijn en goed met elkaar kunnen koppelen. Daarnaast moet de techniek achter de oplossing ook van deze tijd zijn.
5.10	Firm Size	3	3	3	Kleinere bedrijven gaat het makkelijker om zaken te

					accepteren en adopteren dan grotere bedrijven.
5.11	IT managers Support	4	4	4	Zelfde als top management support, maar dan op IT management niveau.
5.12	Service level agreements and monitoring	5	5	5	Hoe snel kun je bij calamiteiten tijdens het project support krijgen, dit heeft zeker invloed op adoptie. Vandaar deze hoge score.
5.13	Regulatory environment	5	5	5	Vind het belangrijk dat de oplossing voldoet aan de wet en regelgeving anders wordt je hier als broker ook op aangekeken.
5.14	Service Providers support	5	5	5	Vindt dit heel belangrijk.
5.15	Perceived industry pressure	3	3	3	Je merkt dat het bij klanten rond gaat waardoor andere klanten ook graag over willen gaan op deze nieuwe technologie.

5. Please explain why

Zie tabel bij vraag 4.

6. Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

Nee, denk dat dit toch wel behoorlijk omvattend is.

7. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

Ik denk in het hele kader van persoonsgegevens bescherming dat overheid wel steeds meer grip zal willen hebben op Cloud adopties. Maar je merkt zelf ook wel dat mensen meer op hun hoede zijn door de hele AVG regelgeving.

8. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

Zoals in vorige punt ook aangegeven, denk ik wel dat de focus op security ook bij IT meer over voorgrond staat. Waar het in verleden nog wel eens door vingers werd gezien, zijn mensen door de AVG wetgeving wel meer bewust van de gegevens waar ze mee omgaan en ligt er ook meer focus op security.

Company: KEMBIT

Function: Enterprise Architect

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS

Cloud is een natuurlijke, tot nu toe resultaat van een revolutie. Je ziet het al jaren lang dat de IT complexer wordt en bedrijven hebben behoefte om hun problemen te out-sourcen. Je zag dit eerst in datacenter-housing. Men hoefde niet meer intern de zaken te housen, niet bezig zijn met rack-spacing, voeding, koeling. Allemaal zaken die niks te maken hebben met je corebusiness. Bedrijven zetten het daardoor vroeger buiten de deur en zetten de housing ergens anders. Vervolgens ging men kijken om de platformen, windows servers, sharepoint server, exchange servers te kunnen outsourcen omdat de wereld complexer wordt. Daarin de nextstep om de management van die capabilities nog verder naar buiten toe te trekken en de technische applicatie beheer van de laag erboven wat op IaaS komt ook weer te kunnen outsourcen. Het is een next step in de evolutie, wat na SaaS de volgende stap zou zijn, space computing?

Het is dus een natuurlijke evolutie, je ziet het al jaren gebeuren en het komt steeds omdat IT complexer wordt en daarmee de core beheerfuncties minder belangrijk zijn.

2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution

Bij klanten die van een on-premises omgeving wordt gemigreerd naar een SaaS omgeving denkt KEMBIT alleen maar aan cloud adoptie. Walter heeft een cloud evolutie model, dit zijn de verschillende fases waarin een bedrijf kan zitten in haar cloud adoptie. Er zijn 5 fases waarbij fase 1 on-premises is en fase 5 alles cloud based is. Ziet zelf dat de meeste bedrijven in fase 3 zitten. Wat houdt 3 in, een organisatie speelt met Office365, speelt met Sharepoint en Onedrive voor zijn bestanden opslag en speelt met Salesforce en nog paar zaken als Cloud applicaties maar de Core applicaties zijn nog steeds on-premises en lokaal gericht. Stap 4 is de stap naar Cloud adoptie het aller grootste.

In stap 4 ga je als gebruiker naar een ander type werkplek. Hierbij is de wijziging het aller grootste voor de gebruiker en dit heeft de grootste impact op de adoptie. Software is van een on-premises applicatie naar een web applicatie is niet de grootste factor, de grootste factor zit in de data opslag. Want zodra je naar fase 4 gaat moet ook je dataopslag mee gaan. Als je alle applicaties in de Cloud hebt maar je data is alleen benaderbaar via een legacy systeem via bijvoorbeeld Citrix heb je niks bereikt want dan heb je uiteindelijk een Citrix werkplek met SaaS applicaties en dat is niet wat je wilt. Citrix moet alleen nog maar zijn ter ondersteuning van legacy meuk.

Dat betekent wil je volledig SaaS gaan, dat de beleving van de werkplek heel anders wordt. Want mensen zijn vanaf Windows 95 gewend aan de Windows verkenner en hangen hier heel sterk aan vast. En je data ontsluiting, alles wat ze kennen is de verkenner. Als je dit in een keer dit los laat dan zie je dat de adoptie heel laag is. Tools als bijvoorbeeld Microsoft Teams, helpen de gebruikers richting dit verkennen gevoel waardoor de emotionele stap lager wordt om de adoptie van het nieuwe product te kunnen krijgen.

Wat je nu ook ziet zijn de capabilities om Cloud resources via de verkenner te ontsluiten via meerdere mogelijkheden helpt je in de next step van de adoptie en transitie fase waardoor ze uiteindelijk de verkenner los kunnen laten. Daarnaast hoe groter het bedrijf hoe moeilijker dit is.

Wat heel snel naar fase 5 kunnen zijn zorg instellingen, omdat hun applicatie portfolio is bepalend voor jouw werkplek type, voor je versaaing. Dus zijn je core applicaties omzetbaar naar SaaS. Dit kan alleen als je als bedrijf een vrij generiek bedrijfsmodel hebt waar minder niche spelers inzitten. Bij een zorginstelling is de core applicatie een ECD. Dit is inmiddels al SaaS, dan is het veel makkelijker om volledig SaaS te worden dan dat je Core applicatie legacy is en de leverancier 0 intentie heeft om dit te gaan versaaen.

3. What is your experience with cloud adoption? What went well, what were Pit Falls?

Went well:

Het maakt het gemakkelijker als een bedrijf tech-savy is. Een bedrijf waar het heel makkelijk ging was het personeel technisch en wiskundige. Dit maakt het veel makkelijker dan een zorg bedrijf waar het personeel geen interesse in IT heeft. De interesse in IT helpt, als het personeel van een bedrijf dus geen interesse in IT heeft is de adoptie moeilijker. Daarnaast moeten ze ook de voordelen van SaaS zien. Als het waren een bedrijf moet de snoepjes krijgen waarmee bedrijven voordeel krijgen. Adoptie zit in snoepjes. Dus hoeveel voordeel krijgt het nieuwe bedrijf met de nieuwe oplossing. Hoe meer voordeel hoe beter de verandering wordt geaccepteerd.

Pit Falls:

Bij een klant die volledig SaaS is gegaan met als businessdriver vanwege IT & kosten en niet eindgebruikersperspectief. Hierbij vond de eindgebruiker het heel moeilijk om de oude denkwijze en werkwijze los te laten en te wennen aan de nieuwe werkwijze en applicaties. Als je van te voren heel veel vrijheid hebt en vervolgens door SaaS een lock down in je mogelijkheden hebt dan wordt adoptie minder.

4. From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important

		Overall	IT Governance	Architecture	Explain why
5.1	Information Security	3	2	5	Informatie security is makkelijker in te regelen in de Cloud omdat er meerdere mogelijkheden zijn om het te beveiligen. Het is een nadeel omdat security vertragend is en daarom geen 5. Het is wel belangrijk maar het draagt niet echt bij tot succes. Deze is lager omdat dit moeilijker is te beveiligen in een Cloud model dan in een on-premises.
5.2	Data Security	4	4	4	Zelfde antwoord als bij Information Security.
5.3	Cost	3	3	3	Kosten worden kunstmatig verlaagd in de Cloud omdat on-premises kosten worden verhoogd. Het is wel positief omdat je van een capex model naar een opex model. Dit vinden bedrijven prettiger.
5.4	Relative advantage	4	4	4	Je flexibiliteit is hoger, maar het is dezelfde flexibiliteit die je in on-premises hebt. Het komt vooral vanwege de verhoogde lifecycle replacement in Cloud en daar zit je voordeel in. Nieuwe features die beschikbaar komen en die je kunt gebruiken.
5.5	Complexity	2	4	5	SaaS is complexiteit verhogend. Interfaces zijn complexer in SaaS

					dan lokaal. Dit verhoogt de complexiteit.
5.6	Compatibility	3	4	4	Compatibility op applicatie niveau is lager op SaaS, je kunt namelijk minder customizen. Het is hoger omdat het op ieder platform werkt en dat laatste weegt iets zwaarder.
5.7	Trialability	4	4	4	Je kunt makkelijker test systemen in de lucht zetten en is daardoor makkelijker te testen.
5.8	Top Management Support	4	4	4	Top management heeft een vrij lage technische requirement. Wel een hoge flexibiliteit requirement. Aangezien SaaS op het internet te benaderen is en daardoor heel flexibel is deze hoge score.
5.9	Technological Readiness	5	5	5	Bij SaaS is de focus op doorontwikkeling, vandaar dat dit een 5 krijgt.
5.10	Firm Size	5	5	5	Het maakt heel veel uit en daardoor een 5. Kleinere bedrijven gaat makkelijker en grote bedrijven zijn log en is de adoptie moeilijker.
5.11	IT managers Support	4	4	4	Je gaat een transitie in vanuit personeelsperspectief omdat beheer wordt gezet vanuit een beheerrol waarvoor ze niet zijn opgeleid. Dit gaat veranderen en het is belangrijk dat de IT manager hier op stuurt.
5.12	Service level agreements and monitoring	5	5	5	De capabilities van service management zijn ingebouwd in SaaS applicaties waardoor het dus makkelijker is om te hanteren.
5.13	Regulatory environment	5	5	5	Succes van SaaS applicatie zou ondermijnd kunnen worden als dit niet voor elkaar is.

5.14	Service Providers support	5	5	5	De complexiteit van de eindgebruiker wordt veel groter. Als je service provider dit niet goed kan ondersteunen verlies je heel snel de adoptie van de SaaS applicatie.
5.15	Perceived industry pressure	1	1	2	Succes zit niet in of een applicatie SaaS is of niet. Maar of de functie van de applicatie voldoet niet de ontsluiting ervan.

5. Please explain why

Zie tabel bij vraag 4.

6. Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

Consumerization of IT, mensen willen het zelfde gemak als thuis binnen hun werk. Business loopt meestal achter op de consumermarkt met opties en flexibiliteit. Dit is een factor die mee weegt vanuit eindgebruiker perspectief. Mensen verwachten ook een hele snelle update cycle door de apps die ze thuis gebruiken en die continue geupdate en nieuwe features bevatten. Dit willen ze ook op hun werk terug zien.

7. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

Technisch beheer gaat dood. Bedrijven die richten op klassieke IT en beheer gaan het niet overleven. De wereld verschuift van Governance naar functioneel beheer en Architectuur. Je beheert niet meer techniek maar beheert het functioneel model van bestaande techniek. Dat is een shift waar je langzamerhand in gaat zitten. Verwachting dat dit voelbaar is binnen 3 jaar.

8. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

Wordt veel hoger, de complexiteit van Cloud resources zijn eilandjes. Je moet de eilandjes laten werken alsof het een groot land bent. Omdat te managen wordt architectuur steeds belangrijker.

Company: Mercedes Benz

Function: Lead Service Architect Infrastructure

1. What is your vision about cloud more specific, SaaS

geen voorkeur voor mensen die aan de infrastructuur zijn. Cloud adoptie komt niet van de grond. Volg trends van cloud sinds 2011. Opgevallen is in het begin, niet de techiek is beïndrukkend. Want wat we op een lokaal datacenter doen zou je ook als SaaS zien. Cloud heeft beetje meer automatie. Maar de achterliggende techniek is niet nu. Maar adoptie graad is de cloud aan het pushen. En economische impact. Infrastructuur is goedkoper in cloud dan. (IaaS zal goedkoper zijn als onpremise) Tot kost van ownership zal goedkoper zijn. Cloud is niet een cure all, maar een middel. voor sommige usecase is het goed. voor sommige niet. Standardisation & automation strategy is heel belangrijk. oplossing cloud on ramping heel interessant voor de toekomst. hoe meer je naar SaaS gaat hoe meer governance je verliest. Governance en security gaat ten koste van rapid time to market. on premise, high governance, high security. (lead time) met cloud gaat ondemand heel snel. maar gaat ten koste van high governance en security. Cloud strategy en governance heel belangrijk.

2. Were you thinking about cloud adoption before moving to a cloud solution

dacht er al na over sinds 2011. servers snel nodig. Shift van capacity requirements. Wordt niet veel overnageacht. Over cloud adoptie maar heeft diepgaande consequenties. Meer beperkt tot het technische vlak. Je loopt intern tegen problemen aan, en dat zijn meestal leadtimes. Cloud oplossing is een methodiek om toch tijdig te leveren maar, wordt te kort over nagedacht. Governance etc mist meestal

3. What is your experience with cloud adoption? What went well, what were Pit Falls?

veel pilots gedaan, maar niet echt cloud adoptatie. Is een grote learning curve, als je nu bv naar Microsoft cloud gaat, veranderd je stack. Dus je moet eenvoud in achterhoofd houden. Hoe ziet architecture eruit mbt bedrijfsapplicatie.

Went well:

Pit Falls:

grootste probleem is, hybrid cloud. Billing was totaal niet transparant. Hoe de kosten basis was, was heel onduidelijk. Billing vaak hoog achteraf kosten. Spullen in de cloud zetten kost niks. Maar spullen eruithalen kost veel.

4. From below CSF's please rate them between 1 and 5. 5 being important and 1 not important

		Overall	IT Governance	Architecture	Explain why
5.1	Information Security	5	5	4	is heel belangrijk als begrijp je niet waar het om gaat (reputation etc) bij governance eigenlijk 6, omdat je geen idee waar je data is, wie heeft toegang. Etc. // Architecture is niet zo belangrijk. Process wel, maar technische architectuur is niet meer relevant
5.2	Data Security	5	5	4	is heel belangrijk als begrijp je niet waar het om gaat (reputatie etc) (Data is oil) Heel belangrijk. Architectuur in cloud model, is data minder van belang data theft en data loss is wel belangrijk. Maar technische onderbouwing minder belangrijk
5.3	Cost	4	4	4	Je gaat naar de cloud voor de kosten. Maar is afhankelijk van de usecase. Maar is niet key enabler voor cloud.// Goed inzicht hebben van kosten voor governance. Moet weten wat een het kost. // EA moet ook aan kosten denken. Alle eigenschappen moet je benutten. snelle diensten zou je snel kunnen helpen en zou het kunnen helpen
5.4	Relative advantage	5	5	5	Nieuwe functies kunnen helpen met architectuur
5.5	Complexity	3	3	2	niet zo relevant, puur om wille van het feit van ontzorgen. Maakt je niet druk om de backend architectuur.
5.6	Compatibility	4	3	4	Belangrijk de trend die je ziet. Cloud zijn de nieuwe silos. Van cloud naar cloud wisselen is niet zo makkelijk. Wordt vaak onderschat. Cloud kan ook heel

					goed vendor lock-in zijn. Compatibiliteit (multicloud) is heel belangrijk. Architectuur is heel belangrijk. Governance moet dan ook duidelijk zijn
5.7	Trialability	4	4	4	Veel valkuilen kan vermijden. Governance model sluit aan op de functies en capabilities van cloud platform
5.8	Top Management Support	4	4	4	heel belangrijk anders krijg je shadow IT. Heel belangrijk dat hele achter organisatie achter staat
5.9	Technological Readiness	5	4	5	Cloud is enabler, geen cure all. Technische slagvaardigheid om naar klaar te gaan, is heel belangrijk. Intergratie naar cloud moet goed gefundeert zijn. Informatie systemen voor zowel gov en EA moet in line zijn met wat de cloud kan leveren. . Als er op governance geen sync is.
5.10	Firm Size	4	5	4	bij kleine bedrijven wat minder belangrijker
5.11	IT managers Support	5	5	5	
5.12	Service level agreements and monitoring	5	5	3	Bij cloud adoptie. Service level agreement is eigen barometer dat je hebt. Hoe onderliggende architectuur is, is niet zo relevant.
5.13	Regulatory environment	5	5	5	kan je niet omheen
5.14	Service Providers support	5	5	3	governancemodel moet erop aangesloten (allemaal geborgen in slas)
5.15	Perceived industry pressure	3	3	3	2015/2016 was die fase wel. Nu minder relevant.

5. Please explain why

Zie tabel bij vraag 4.

6. Are there any success factors missing in the previous question?

De lijst dekt het goed af.

7. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to governance in relation to cloud adoption?

none

8. What kind of expectations do you have with regards to Architecture in relation to cloud adoption.

none